

科学计量学工具画册

Tools Gallery for Scientometrics Research

李杰 博士/副研究员 中国科学院文献情报中心

李杰博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

《科学计量学导论》配套素材

《科学计量学导论》

科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书
信息资源管理专业推荐教材

丛书主编: 李 杰

Introduction to
Scientometrics

科学计量学导论

李 杰 著

科学计量学是量化的科学学，
目标是创建一个可持续的科学发现与研究生态。
Scientometrics is the quantitative science of science,
with the goal of creating a sustainable ecosystem
for scientific discovery and research.

 首都经济贸易大学出版社
Capital University of Economics and Business Press

李杰, 科学计量学导论[M]. 北京: 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

《科学计量学手册》

科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书

Scientometricpedia: of the community, by the community, for the community.

Handbook of Scientometrics

科学计量学手册

李杰 张琳 黄颖 ◎ 主编

陈悦 胡志刚 杨思洛 ◎ 副主编

Scientometrics:
Making the scientific system
more open and transparent!

科学计量学：
让科学系统更开放、更透明！

 首都经济贸易大学出版社
Capital University of Economics and Business Press

李杰，张琳，黄颖等. 科学计量学手册[M]. 北京：
首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2024.

科学自身是美的，可视化是来呈现科学之美！

使一个方程具有美感，比使他去符合实验更重要。

狄拉克 (1902-1984)
量子力学创始人之一

当大自然把我们引向一个前所未有的和异常美丽的数学形式时，我们将不得不相信它们是真的。

海森堡 (1901-1976)
量子力学创始人之一

科学知识图谱工具图集

Research Gate

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李杰科学网博客: <https://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

编号	软件名称	开发者	功能描述
1	BibeR	Yang Liu 等	在线文献统计及可视化
2	BibExcel	Olle Persson	科学计量与可视化前处理
3	Bicomb	崔雷等	矩阵的提取和统计 (中文)
4	CoCites-Co-Citation Tool	Citation Labs	网页共引分析
5	Carrot2	Audilio Gonzales 等	辅助文本可视化
6	CiteSpace	Chaomei Chen	科学计量与可视化分析
7	CitNetExplorer	Nees Jan van Eck 等	引证网络及可视化
8	CRExplorer	Andreas Thor 等	数据转换及文献谱分析
9	Gephi	Gephi 团队	网络可视化分析
10	GPS Visualizer	Adam Schneider	在线辅助地理可视化
11	HistCite	Eugene Garfield	科学计量及引证网络
12	Nails-HAMMER	Juho Salminen 等	在线可视化分析
13	Jigsaw	John Stasko 等	辅助文本可视化
14	KnowledgeMatrix Plus	KISTI	科学计量可视化分析
15	Leydesdorff Toolkit	Loet Leydesdorff	科学计量与可视化前处理
16	MapEquation	Daniel Edler 等	在线网络及演化的可视化
17	MATLAB 语言	Giuseppe Cardillo	科学计量分析
18	Netdraw	Stephen Borgatti 等	网络可视化分析
19	NodeXL Basic	Cody Dunne 等	网络可视化分析
20	Open Knowledge Maps	Peter Kraker 等	在线文献可视化分析
21	Pajek	Vladimir Batagelj 等	网络可视化分析
22	Publish or Perish	Anne-Wil Harzing	谷歌学术数据采集及分析
23	Python 语言 - BiblioTods	Sebastian Grauwin	科学计量分析
24	Python 语言 - Metaknowledge	Reid McIlroy-Young 等	科学计量数据可视化
25	RPYS i/o	Jordan Comins 等	在线文献时间谱分析
26	R 语言 - Bibliometrix	Massimo Aria 等	科学计量分析
27	R 语言 - CITAN	Marek Gagolewski	科学计量分析
28	Social Network Visualizer	Dimitris V. Kalamaras	网络可视化分析
29	SATI	刘启元	矩阵的提取和统计 (中文)
30	Scholarometer	Fil Menczer 等	在线引证分析和影响评价
31	SCI of SCI	Katy Börner 等	科学计量与可视化分析
32	ScienceScape	Mathieu Jacomy	在线文献计量及可视化
33	SciMAT	Manolo J. Cobo 等	科学计量与可视化分析
34	STICCI.eu	Valentín Gómez-Jáuregui 等	数据预处理和转换
35	Visone	Ulrik Brandes 等	网络可视化
36	VOSviewer	Nees Jan van Eck 等	科学计量与可视化分析
37	Voyant Tools	Stéfan Sinclair 等	全文本挖掘及可视化
38	WoS2 Pajek	Viadimir Batagelj	网络文件处理
39	WoS Network Tool	ECOOM	在线合作网络和文献耦合
40	Webometric Analyst	Mike Thelwall 等	网络计量学分析

科学知识图谱原理及应用

——VOSviewer 和 CitNetExplorer 初学者指南

Principles and Applications of Mapping Knowledge Domains
A Beginner's Guide to VOSviewer and CitNetExplorer

李杰 著

本书顾问:

(荷) Nees Jan van Eck (尼斯·扬·凡·艾克)

(荷) Ludo Waltman (卢多·瓦特曼)

高等教育出版社

来源: 李杰. 科学知识图谱原理及应用.[M].北京: 高等教育出版社. 2018.

CiteSpace

<https://citespace.podia.com/>

- CiteSpace绘制的陈超美教授论文的参考文献共被引网络

VOS viewer

<https://www.vosviewer.com/>

- VOS viewer绘制的中国科学技术大学火灾实验室师生网络

VOSviewer Online

<https://app.vosviewer.com/>

VOSviewer Online

Visualizing scientific landscapes

VOSviewer Online is a tool for network visualization. It is a web-based version of VOSviewer, a popular tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks, such as co-authorship networks, citation networks, and co-occurrence networks.

Using VOSviewer Online, visualizations of bibliometric networks created by VOSviewer can be explored interactively in a web browser. To open a visualization, use the button at the top right or click one of the example visualizations below.

More information about VOSviewer Online is provided in [VOSviewer Online Docs](#) and in [these introduction videos](#).

Close

Gephisto

grants you a network map in one click

<https://jacomyma.github.io/gephisto/>

Gephisto

grants you a network map in one click.

- Gephisto绘制的我国学者在Scientometrics上论文的合作网络。

The node sizes and positions are from the original data. The node colors depend on the attribute modularity_class: in blue is 8; in pink is 5; in green is 9; in red is 1; in yellow is 3; and in grey are the other modalities. Gatherings of nodes with the same modularity_class were highlighted by a color contour corresponding to their modality. Edges are directed and drawn as straight lines. Edges are weighted in the data, but their weight has been ignored for this visualization. Made by Gephisto.

Tableau

<https://www.tableau.com/zh-cn>

• Tableau对全科学领域期刊分类的可视化

Scopus期刊聚类

李杰, lijie_jerry@126.com

说明: Leydesdorff用VOSViewer软件制作的较新的基础图谱。本图在Loet数据的基础上使用Tableau进行了可视化。

Web of Science期刊聚类

李杰, lijie_jerry@126.com

说明: Leydesdorff用VOSViewer软件制作的较新的基础图谱。本图在Loet数据的基础上使用Tableau进行了可视化。

Scimago Graphica

<https://graphica.app/>

- 兰州文献情报中心作者的合作网络

weight < documents >

cluster

Graphia

<https://graphia.app/>

- 兰州文献情报中心作者的合作网络

Graphinsight

<https://github.com/CarloNicolini/GraphInsight>

<https://carlonicolini.github.io/sections/software>

- 海事风险研究的作者合作网络

3dSciLi: Scientific Literature Network

Visualization in 3d

<http://3dscili.scienceontheweb.net/>

- 对Safety Science 期刊2020-2021年数据的分析

J. Swacha, "Three Dimensions of Science: A Web Tool for 3D Visualization of Scientific Literature," 2021 ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL), 2021, pp. 274-277, doi: 10.1109/JCDL52503.2021.00082.

Giovanni's citation network

<https://uoa-eresearch.github.io/citations/?data=Giovanni>

Orange Data Mining

<https://orangedatamining.com/>

- 《雪崩》施引文献的主题分布

• 元宇宙施引论文的空间分布

1 《雪崩》施引文献的时间趋势

2 《雪崩》施引文献的空间分布

Period: 2000-2021

Total Publications: 609

Total Citations: 6347

H5-Index: 32

Metrics

Average H5-Index

Top 100 Organizations: 48.2

Top 100 Authors: 5.6

Average Citations

All years: 10.4

Last 10 years: 10.1

Last 5 years: 10.1

Focus Areas i

Computer Science

Artificial Intelligence 102nd

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机构名: 中英文名

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全球学者库通过大数据处理与分析技术, 能够汇总同一学者的绝大多数论文。
但也有少部分例外。如果“学者本人”发现搜索到“多个自己”(如何查验), 请点击注册填报信息。
读者注册后可以免费订阅1位学者, 跟踪与查看Ta们的全部论文, 非注册用户只能查看前10篇论文。

文献排名

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2022-05

2021年度中国风湿免疫病领域高价...

本推荐表是在系统全面准确地统计中国机构作者发表的风湿免疫病领域国际论文的基础上(说明: 风湿免疫病领域专家为主要完成人发表的全部论文...

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2022-04

2021年度中国呼吸与危重症医学领...

本推荐表是在系统全面准确地统计中国机构作者发表的呼吸与危重症医学领域国际论文的基础上(说明: 呼吸与危重症医学领域专家为主要完成人发...

24

2022-04

2021年度中国妇产与生殖医学科领...

本推荐表是在系统全面准确地统计中国机构作者发表的妇产与生殖医学领域国际论文的基础上(说明: 妇产与生殖医学领域专家为主要完成人发表...

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国际论文数 336+

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学术论文

代表作

合作学者

学科

期刊

Email

发文曾用名

机构轨迹

1 The principle of preservation of probability and the generalized density evolution equation

来源: STRUCT SAF(P 0167-4730 E) 发表时间: 2008/01

类型: 期刊论文 为本人加分: 25156.900965

2 The equivalent extreme-value event and evaluation of the structural system reliability

来源: STRUCT SAF(P 0167-4730 E 1879-3355) 发表时间: 2007/01

类型: 期刊论文 为本人加分: 24863.268562

3 The extreme value distribution and dynamic reliability analysis of nonlinear structures with uncerta..

来源: STRUCT SAF(P 0167-4730 E) 发表时间: 2007/01

类型: 期刊论文 为本人加分: 20110.505635

CSET Map of Science

https://sciencemap.cset.tech/?selected_filters=check---growth-3-yr-pctile%2Ccheck---pct-ai-papers%2Ccheck---subject

CSET Map of Science

The CSET Map of Science is a map of scholarly literature constructed by clustering research publications and organizing research clusters (RCs) based on citation linkages. This map can be used for a range of analytic tasks (see our [data snapshot series](#) for some example analyses). The publications in the map are drawn from a set of [merged](#) scholarly literature we have constructed from Microsoft Academic Graph, Clarivate Web of Science, the Chinese National Knowledge Infrastructure, Dimensions Digital Science, arXiv, and Papers with Code. Our corpus covers all years of each of these sources with the exception of papers published before 2000 in Clarivate Web of Science and papers published before 2005 in the Chinese National Knowledge Infrastructure. The Microsoft Academic Graph project will be discontinued at the end of 2021. We clustered the merged dataset into ~100,000 research clusters and mapped the clusters based on shared citations. For more information on our methodology, see sections 2.1 and 2.2 in [this research paper](#).

Our Map of Science is shown below. Once it has loaded, you can filter the visible research clusters (click on "More Filters" to see more options). Cluster proximity represents the strength of the citation links between clusters. The default cluster size is based on the number of papers published in the last five years, and unless otherwise indicated all filter metrics are also based on the papers published during that period. Hovering over a cluster will show you some summary information about that cluster, and clicking on a cluster will take you to a details page with much more information, such as prominent authors, papers, and funders based on the last five years of publications. Use the graph toolbar to switch between pan and zoom.

Contributors to the Map of Science include Ilya Rahkovsky, Jennifer Melot, Autumn Toney, Sara Abdulla, James Dunham, Daniel Chou, Rebecca Gelles, Catherine Aiken, and Dewey Murdick, and the clustering approach was based on a method developed by SciTech Strategies. The contributors would like to thank Ashwin Acharya, Helen Toner, Zachary Arnold, Igor Mikolic-Torreira, Patrick Lee, Bryan Ware and others at Next5, and Avital Percher for their advice and feedback. It was last updated on 2022-06-27, and we intend to update it quarterly going forward. Please [contact us](#) with any questions, corrections, or suggestions.

<https://paperscape.org/>

<https://paperscape.org/>

<https://my.paperscape.org/>

Manylines

<https://medialab.sciencespo.fr/en/tools/manylines/>

manylines

NOT SAVED YET

SciencesPo. médialab

1 new network 2 basemap 3 take views 4 narratives

cortex

<https://managerv2.cortex.net/dashboard>

The screenshot shows the Cortex dashboard interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a logo, a 'dashboard' button, and a dropdown menu currently showing 'project' and 'safety science'. Below this, there are three main action buttons: 'upload file' (pink), 'start script' (green), and 'start discussion' (yellow). On the left side, there is a 'Your analyses' section with a list of recent analyses, including 'Data Parsing' and 'Network Mapping' with timestamps and status icons. Below that is a 'datasets' section with a list of datasets like '3d', 'rted', 're', 'li-s-database-converted', 'data', and '4074wos-1991-2020'. The main content area displays a file explorer view for a project named 'network mapping' with a sub-project '4074wos-1991-2020'. It shows folders like '/mapexplorer' and '/maps', and a file 'hnetwork-1991_2020hn-4074wos-1991-20201991_2020top150-Author-Author-....gexf - 144.48 kB'. There are also analysis logs with dates and IDs.

Tubes Layout

Text Visualization Browser

Text Visualization Browser
A Visual Survey of Text Visualization Techniques (IEEE PacificVis 2015 short paper)
Provided by ISOVIS group

[About](#) [Summary](#) [Add entry](#)

Techniques displayed: **440**

Search:

Time filter: 1976 2019

Analytic Tasks

- Sum
- Avg
- Max
- Min
- Stdev
- Sort
- Filter
- Group
- Aggregate

Visualization Tasks

- Star
- Hide
- Show
- Zoom
- Pan
- Rotate
- Reset

Data

Source

Mapping Wikipedia with bert and UMAP

<https://home.nomic.ai/visxwiki>

NOMIC

presents:

Mapping Wikipedia with BERT and UMAP

**Brandon
Duderstadt**

Nomic AI

**Andriy
Mulyar**

Nomic AI

**Ben
Schmidt**

Nomic AI
NYU

To appear at VisXAI 2022

Introduction

NOMIC

presents:

Mapping Wikipedia with BERT and UMAP

**Brandon
Duderstadt**

Nomic AI

**Andriy
Mulyar**

Nomic AI

**Ben
Schmidt**

Nomic AI
NYU

To appear at VisXAI 2022

Introduction

In 2018, Devlin et al. introduced BERT, ¹ a neural language model that can be trained to produce general purpose representations of language called **pretrained embeddings**. Using a process called **transfer learning**, these pretrained embeddings can be used to dramatically reduce the amount of labeled data and computing power required to train AI on downstream tasks.

The practical utility of transfer learning has led to near ubiquitous industrial adoption of pretrained embeddings.

Concurrently, research interest in **foundation models**, or models like BERT that produce pretrained embeddings using large bodies of unstructured data, has increased dramatically.

ScienceScape

<https://medialab.github.io/sciencescape/>

ScienceScape

Helpers for scientometrics. Convert files, get networks, visualize stuff from Scopus or Web of Knowledge.

Get Networks

Visualize and download networks of keywords and/or authors and/or journals, and more.

Scopus Web of Knowledge

Reference Scape

Visualize and download networks using a landscape of references

Scopus

Papers over time

Visualize how many papers are published each year in your file

Scopus Web of Knowledge

Keywords over time

Visualize and download the use of each keyword over time in your file

Scopus Web of Knowledge

- climate change (4)
- adaptation (1356)
- vulnerability (534)
- global warming (4)
- resilience (367)
- temperature (270)
- drought (224)
- agriculture (197)

2011

- second life 9 papers
- virtual worlds 7 papers
- metaverse 4 papers
- metaverses 4 papers
- education 4 papers
- language learning 2 papers
- virtual reality 1 paper
- e-learning 1 paper
- immersion 1 paper
- collaboration 1 paper

2012

- metaverse 7 papers
- virtual worlds 4 papers
- metaverses 3 papers
- e-learning 2 papers
- ciberarchitecture 2 papers
- cyberculture 2 papers
- fictionalisation 2 papers
- new virtual narratives 2 papers
- virtual reality and hypertext 2 papers
- virtual environments 1 paper

2013

- second life 5 papers
- metaverse 3 papers
- virtual worlds 3 papers
- metaverses 3 papers
- immersion 2 papers
- avatars 2 papers
- performance 2 papers
- avatar 1 paper
- mixed reality 1 paper
- education 1 paper

2014

- virtual worlds 3 papers
- metaverse 2 papers
- second life 2 papers
- avatar 2 papers
- 3d 2 papers
- art 2 papers
- virtual reality 1 paper
- metaverses 1 paper
- artificial intelligence 1 paper
- simulation 1 paper

2015

- metaverse 3 papers
- second life 3 papers
- virtual worlds 1 paper
- metaverses 1 paper
- e-learning 1 paper
- 3d 1 paper
- art 1 paper
- metaverse retailing 1 paper
- visualization 1 paper
- process 1 paper

2016

- metaverse 3 papers
- second life 3 papers
- virtual worlds 2 papers
- virtual reality 1 paper
- avatar 1 paper
- immersion 1 paper
- presence 1 paper
- metaverse retailing 1 paper
- representation 1 paper
- serious games 1 paper

2017

- metaverse 4 papers
- virtual reality 2 papers
- augmented reality 2 papers
- avatar 2 papers
- virtual environments 2 papers
- virtual worlds 1 paper
- second life 1 paper
- mixed reality 1 paper
- education 1 paper
- 3d 1 paper

2018

- metaverse 4 papers
- mixed reality 2 papers
- virtual environments 2 papers
- virtual worlds 1 paper
- second life 1 paper
- virtual world 1 paper
- opensim 1 paper
- blockchain 1 paper
- telepresence 1 paper
- definition 1 paper

2019

- metaverse 2 papers
- second life 1 paper
- augmented reality 1 paper
- virtual world 1 paper
- educational technology 1 paper
- gaming 1 paper
- social networks 1 paper
- coevolution 1 paper
- didactic material 1 paper
- economics 1 paper

2020

- metaverse 5 papers
- emerging technologies 2 papers
- augmented reality 1 paper
- avatar 1 paper
- education 1 paper
- immersion 1 paper
- opensim 1 paper
- representation 1 paper
- innovation 1 paper
- moodle 1 paper

2021

- metaverse 12 papers
- virtual reality 3 papers
- augmented reality 3 papers
- deep learning 3 papers
- aircraft maintenance education 2 papers
- avatar 1 paper
- mixed reality 1 paper
- virtual world 1 paper
- extended reality 1 paper

2022

- metaverse 60 papers
- virtual reality 20 papers
- augmented reality 14 papers
- mixed reality 8 papers
- extended reality 7 papers
- artificial intelligence 5 papers
- avatars 3 papers
- vr 3 papers
- 0 3 papers
- blockchain 3 papers

citationchaser

<https://estech.shinyapps.io/citationchaser/>

citationchaser

Home

Article input

References

Citations

Analysis

Network

Enter the articles that you want to start from. We will first check the full citations in the Lens.org database. You must complete this step before retrieving references and citations.

EITHER:

1: Paste your identifiers in (each id separated from the next using a comma, carriage return (new line), or space)

Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)

10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105093

Microsoft Academic identifiers (MAGIDs)

separate identifiers with a comma

PubMed identifiers (PMIDs)

separate identifiers with a comma

CORE identifiers (COREIDs)

separate identifiers with a comma

Visualise the citation network

Once you have loaded your input articles and searched for references and citations, you will be able to visualise your network here. Please be aware that large citation networks (n before visualising the network.

The network visualisation may take a few moments to generate. Zoom in and out using your mouse wheel or two fingers on a trackpad. Move around the network by clicking and d

60 YEARS OF AI RESEARCH*

<https://60years.vizhub.ai/>

60 YEARS OF AI RESEARCH*

by Hendrik Strobelt and Benjamin Hoover from MIT-IBM Watson AI Lab [*more]

FILTER BY SUBSTRING

author title clear

FILTER BY 5-YEAR RANGE

- 1955 - 1959
- 1960 - 1964
- 1965 - 1969
- 1970 - 1974
- 1975 - 1979
- 1980 - 1984
- 1985 - 1989
- 1990 - 1994
- 1995 - 1999
- 2000 - 2004
- 2005 - 2009
- 2010 - 2014
- 2015 -

FILTER BY YEAR

filter:

OPTIONS

reduce overlap (costly)

IEEE VIS Anthology Vis*

<https://visav.vizhub.ai/>

opensyllabus

<https://galaxy.opensyllabus.org/>

OPEN SYLLABUS GALAXY

Search 1M books and articles

SEARCH BOOKS SEARCH SYLLABI

Search for titles and authors
The 1,138,841 most frequently-assigned texts (everything with 5+ appearances)

- #1 **The Elements of Style**
William Strunk
Assigned on 15,533 syllabi
- #2 **A Writer's Reference**
Diana Hacker
Assigned on 14,931 syllabi
- #3 **A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations**
Kate L. Turabian
Assigned on 13,426 syllabi
- #4 **The Communist Manifesto**
Karl Marx
Assigned on 11,234 syllabi
- #5 **The Republic**
Plato
Assigned on 9,883 syllabi
- #6 **Calculus**

citeplag

<https://citeplag.org/reports/compare/6861131/6861251#>

zukünftiger Modifizierungen auf Änderungen der staatsorganisatorischen Struktur beschränkt, wohingegen die meist separat verabschiedeten „Bill of Rights“ meist für unabänderlich erklärt wurden, vgl. R. Taylor, A New Look at Article V and the Bill of Rights, in: 6 Ind. L. Rev. (1973), S. 699 ff. (007 7) — die Liaison von Tradition und Moderne, die Verbindung eines erhaltenden mit einem wandlungsfähigen Element — fand mit der Möglichkeit der Verfassungsergänzung mittels Amendments in Art. V der Verfassung von 1787 erstmalig Einzug in eine Rechtsordnung:

„The Congress, whenever two thirds of both Houses shall deem it necessary, shall propose Amendments to this Constitution, or, on the Application of the Legislatures of two thirds of the several States, shall call a Convention for proposing Amendments, which, in either Case, shall be valid to all Intents and Purposes, as Part of this Constitution, when ratified by the Legislatures of three fourths of the several States, or by Conventions in three fourths thereof, as the one or the other Mode of Ratification may be proposed by the Congress; Provided that no Amendment which may be made prior to the Year One thousand eight hundred and eight shall in any Manner affect the first and fourth Clauses in the Ninth Section of the first Article; and that no State, without its Consent, shall be deprived of its equal Suffrage in the Senate.“

über dem Verfassungskonvent von Philadelphia schwebte — wie erwähnt — stetig der Geist des Kompromisses. Hinsichtlich der Amendmentregelung wurde der Wille zur „aurea mediocritas“ schliesslich exemplarisch umgesetzt, indem man einen Mittelweg fand zwischen einer „fliessenden“, leicht zu ändernden Verfassung, die beispielsweise keinerlei Schutz vor unerwünschtem politischen Wandel geboten hätte, und einer allzu rigiden Ordnung ohne jegliche Möglichkeit zur gelegentlich notwendigen Neuorientierung. Art.V übernahm hierbei eine bedeutsame Rolle.

So konnten noch die Articles of Confederation nicht ohne die Zustimmung der Legislaturen ^{Footnote 4} Der Begriff „legislatures“ in Artikel V bezeichnet „deliberative, representative bodies of the type which in 1789 exercised the legislative power in the several States. It does not comprehend the popular referendum which has subsequently become a part of the legislative process in many of the States, nor may a State validly condition ratification of a proposed constitutional amendment on its approval

The Constitution of the United States Interpretation Congressional Research Service

MODE OF AMENDMENT

ARTICLE V

The Congress, whenever two thirds of both Houses shall deem it necessary, shall propose Amendments to this Constitution, or, on the Application of the Legislatures of two thirds of the several States, shall call a Convention for proposing Amendments, which in either Case, shall be valid to all Intents and Purposes, as Part of this Constitution, when ratified by the Legislatures of three fourths of the several States or by Conventions in three fourths thereof, as the one or the other Mode of Ratification may be proposed by the Congress; Provided that no Amendment which may be made prior to the Year One thousand eight hundred and eight shall in any Manner affect the first and fourth Clauses in the Ninth Section of the first Article; and that no State, without its Consent, shall be deprived of its equal Suffrage in the Senate.

AMENDMENT OF THE CONSTITUTION

Scope of the Amending Power

When this Article was before the Constitutional Convention, a motion to insert a provision that “no State shall without its consent be affected in its internal policy” was made and rejected ^{Footnote 1} 2 M. FARRAND, THE RECORDS OF THE FEDERAL CONVENTION OF 1787 (New Haven: rev. ed. 1937), 630, (001 1) A further attempt to impose a substantive limitation on the amending power was made in 1861, when Congress submitted to the States a proposal to bar any future amendments which would authorize Congress to “interfere, within any State, with the domestic institutions thereof ...” ^{Footnote 2} 57 CONG. GLOBE 1263 (1861), (002 2) Three States ratified this article before the outbreak of the Civil War made it

Footnote 3

Press 'Esc'-key or double click to hide the mask. X

Quantifying the evolution of individual scientific impact

<http://sciencepaths.kimalbrecht.com>

LINES

Line

Publication record of a scientist.

Dots on the line

Publications of the scientist

Height of bumps in the line

Number of citations after ten years for the corresponding paper.

Blue bump

Highest impact paper of a scientist.

Height of line

Number of citations after ten years.

From left to right, we arrange the first to the last paper of a scientist, ignoring their timing of publication.

The position of the highest impact paper of a scientist can be with the same probability, anywhere in her sequence of papers – it could be the first publication, could appear mid-career or could be a scientist's last publication. In other words, impact is randomly distributed within a scientist's body of work, regardless of publication time, order in the sequence of publications, discipline or groups of scientists selected. This result is named "random impact rule". Check the paper for more details!

Nature 150 Interactive

<https://www.nature.com/immersive/d41586-019-03165-4/index.html>

GrantExplorer

<https://grantexplorer.org>

Name	Gnts ↓	Amt
Office of the Director	1075	\$100M
Directorate for Geosciences	809	\$380M
Directorate for Social, Behavioral & Economic Sciences	663	\$81M
Directorate for Biological Sciences	244	\$120M
Directorate for Mathematical & Physical Sciences	239	\$89M
Directorate for Engineering	237	\$40M
Directorate for Computer & Information Science & Engineering	137	\$55M
Directorate for Education & Human Resources	38	\$43M

BibExcel

<https://homepage.univie.ac.at/juan.gorraiz/bibexcel/>

<https://homepage.univie.ac.at/juan.gorraiz/bibexcel/bibexcel.exe>

- BibExcel+Pajek绘制的Scientometrics期刊论文作者合作网络

科学结构图谱 (中国科学院)

<http://sciencemap.casaid.cn/dist/#/>

演变轨迹流 0

Mapping Technology Structure

<http://sciencemap.casaid.cn/pat/#/>

技术结构图谱 2021

272375篇三方专利形成85个技术焦点群组, 7375个技术焦点

サイエスマップ2018(ウェブ版)

サイエスマップは、論文データベース分析により国際的に注目を集めている研究領域を抽出・可視化
サイエスマップの詳細については[こちら](#)をご覧ください。また本サイトの使い方の概要については[こちら](#)

可視化対象:

(国公立大学・大学共同利用機関法人を選択)

可視化対象は国立大学(68)、公立大学(22)、私立大学等(96)、大学共同利用機関法人(4)、国立研究開発法人等(24)、論文の謝辞に
れているファンディング機関等(28)から選択できます。

論文シェア(分数カウント)による領域の表示:

(論文種別を選択)

(国名を選択)

検索条件にあわせて、主要国の参照領域を表示します。

領域群情報 表示 非表示

研究領域群の名前を表示します(研究領域群は目安です)。

地形表示 表示 非表示

地形表示をオーバーレイし

4ナ

2を

論

サイエスマップ2018

- 灰色の円をマウスオーバー 特徴語(上位20程度)の表示
- 灰色の円をマウスクリック 主要国シェアとStreamの表示
- Alt+マウスドラッグ 指定された範囲の特徴語のワードクラウド表示

主要国シェア(分数カウント)

研究領域を示す灰色の円をクリックすると主要国シェアが表示されます。

可視化対象の該当領域数

● 研究領域	--	0
● コアペーパー	1件以上	0
● サइटィングペーパー(Top10%)	1件以上(FA機関等では2件以上)	0
● サइटィングペーパー	2件以上(FA機関等では10件以上)	0
特徴語を含む領域数 + (検索語が複数ある場合、語によって色が異なります)	重複除く	0

SciLand (Science Landscape) Viewer

<https://devgru.nistep.go.jp/scilandview/>

SciLand Viewer

可視化したい対象を選択してください

2012年

日本

Keywordで指定

Submit

可視化結果

カーソルを当てることで、RFに関するいろいろな情報が出てきます

RFの表示

背景のカラー表示

PNG DL

Shape of science

<https://www.scimagojr.com/shapeofscience/>

Arena3D^{web}

<https://bib.fleming.gr:8084/app/arena3d>

iLit4GEE-AI: An Interactive Web App for GEE-AI Literature

https://geoair-lab.github.io/iLit4GEE-AI-WebApp/index.html?fbclid=IwAR1okaT93nVvgf1_BS0syr5e7-5B3JQNxMxraokLQwl3lcCuOPl6c_a6Qzg#

iLit4GEE-AI: An Interactive Web App for GEE-AI Literature

Geospatial distribution of the reviewed/selected papers [reset map](#)

[About the project](#) [Demo video](#) [License & copyright](#) [Abbr list & data explanation](#) [NewDataEntryForm](#)

Institution Country [reset](#)

Published in Journal [reset](#)

Year of Publication [reset](#)

Application Focus [reset](#)

Study Area [reset](#)

RS Data Type [reset](#)

Method/Application [reset](#)

Method (macro) [reset](#)

Method (detailed) [reset](#)

Hierarchy of Methods [reset](#)

State Network Visualizer

<https://www.mapequation.org/state-visualizer/>

Load files
Load Infomap state network (.net) and cluster (_states.clu) files. If no _states.clu file is provided, Infomap v2.5.0 will be run with default parameters and 5 trials.

Lump states
Lump state nodes in the same module and physical node into one state node. Improves performance.

Inter-module links
Control if links whose source and target modules differ should be drawn or not. Regardless, they take part in the simulation.

Node names

Font size

Link distance

Link threshold

Link width

Node charge

By Anton Eriksson (source code)
Les Misérables example data from Netzschleuder
mapequation.org

Alluvial Diagram Generator

<https://www.mapequation.org/alluvial/>

Alluvial Diagram v1.14.0
Powered by Infomap v2.5.0

Load or arrange Help

COLORS
Color scheme: C3 Sinebow

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

Paint Clear all

BY SIMILARITY
Paint modules Paint all

BY NODE ASSIGNMENTS
Paint modules Paint all

BY MODULE ID
Paint modules Paint all

MODULE
Move up Move down
Move left Move right
Expand Contract
Show node list

Network: 1998
Codelength: 8.07 bits

semantic word cloud visualization

Semantic structures derived from abstract information spaces. For small spaces (i.e. less than one hundred nodes), such graphs can be an effective means of reducing high-dimensional information into two or three spatial dimensions. As dimensionality increases, representing the thematic diversity of documents using spatial proximity alone becomes less and less effective. This paper reports an experiment designed to determine whether, for larger spaces, benefits are to be gained from adding visual links between document nodes as an additional means of representing the most important semantic relationships. Two well known algorithms, minimum spanning trees (MST) and pathfinder associative networks (PFNET), were tested against both a scatter graph visualisation, derived from factor analysis, and a traditional list-based hypertext interface. It was hypothesised that visual links would facilitate users' comprehension of the information space with corresponding gains in information seeking performance. Navigation performance and user impressions were analysed across a range of different search tasks. Results indicate both significant performance gains and more positive user feedback for MST and PFNET visualisations over scatter graphs. Performance on all visualisations was generally poorer and never better than that achieved on the text list interface, although the magnitude of these differences was found to be highly task dependent.

C1 Brunel Univ, Dept Informat Syst & Comp, Vivid Res Ctr, Uxbrid

...or try a [random Wikipedia page](#), [Google trend](#), [Twitter trend](#)

Create Word Cloud

[Show Advanced Options](#)

Carrot2

<https://search.carrot2.org/>

Web PubMed

safety culture options Search

Clusters list **treemap** pie-chart

Results list

All retrieved results (998)

1 Management of Calcification: Rational and Technical Considerations for Intravascular Lithotripsy. Techniques in vascular and interventional radiology, 2022. Arterial calcification (AC) is a common complication among patients with peripheral arterial disease (PAD). AC presents various challenges to PAD treatment including an increased likelihood of vessel rupture and dissection, and by acting as a physical barrier to drug delivery by angioplasty balloons. Intravascular lithotripsy (IVL) is a novel intervention that specifically targets AC by emitting s...
KEYWORDS: Calcification, Intravascular, Lithoplasty, Vessel prep
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/35842260>
Disease Management Treatment Efficacy

2 The prevalence, antibiotic resistance and multilocus sequence typing of colistin-resistant bacteria isolated from Penaeus vannamei farms in earthen ponds and HDPE film-lined ponds in China. Journal of fish diseases, 2022. The aquaculture environment, especially the culture ponds and aquaculture products, is considered to be an important reservoir of colistin resistance genes. However, systematic investigations of colistin resistance in Penaeus vannamei farming in different culture modes are scarce. In this study, a total of 93 non-duplicated samples were collected from P. vannamei farms in five cities in China from...
KEYWORDS: Penaeus vannamei, MLST, colistin, multidrug resistance, prevalence
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/35841601>
Significantly P

3 Exploring the embodied carbon flow interactive relationships in China from an ecological network perspective: a model framework and application at provincial level. Environmental science and pollution research international, 2022. Energy-related carbon emissions take a large proportion in China, and the interregional trade caused by provincial disparities has led to significant differences in carbon footprint (CF) and embodied carbon flows among provinces that make great bottlenecks for the balance of economic development and carbon mitigation. In this study, we developed an embodied carbon flow-based ecological network (EC...
KEYWORDS: Ecological network analysis, Embodied carbon flows, Interactive relationships, Multi-regional input-output model, Province-level analysis
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/35841509>
Controlled Study Develop a Model

Rates P (65) Care Data (86) Patients N (53) Primary Treatment (77) Health Data (91) Health Outcomes (60) COVID-19 Safety (85) Risk Factors (68) Safety or Tolerability (54)

Mean 95 (32) Comparative Efficacy (95) Hospital Management (108) Patients Aged (102) Low or very Low (125) Group Compared (104) Aimed to Assess (98) Care were Included (115) Risk of Developing (88) Trial Evaluated (82)

Care Providers (83) Effective and Safe (103) Therapy for Patients (131) Quality Improvement (147) Disease Management (172) Clinical Improvement (138) Effectively Improve (166) Highly Effective (103)

Food Safety (57) Randomized Trials (90) Clinical Data (117) Patient Care (169) Study Group (184) Medications Used (177) Clinical Outcomes (127) Differences between Groups (92)

Human Cells (25) Pain Management (69) Patients with High (99) Treatment Efficacy (144) Clinical Treatment (159) Management and Reporting (134) Controlled Study (170) Increased Significantly (108)

Vaccine Safety (39) Significantly P (105) Review Includes (126) Management Factors (102) Increased Risk (114) Evaluate and Compare (98) Management Model (104) Included Trials (101) Events 95 CI (40)

Identify Risks (86) Health Care (92) Study N (79) Disease Severity (53) Control in Reducing (66) Develop a Model (85) Medication Reviews (60) Data System (76)

Nurses Working (16) Nursing Education (14) Identify Factors (63) Nursing Managers (29) Disease Severity (53) Control in Reducing (66) Cell Therapy (32) Develop a Model (85) Medication Reviews (60) Participants N (27)

FoamTree

PubTrends: Scientific literature explorer

<https://pubtrends.net/>

<https://pubtrends.net/>

PubTrends Pubmed > "human aging" > 1000 Most Cited

- Papers
- Trends
- Network
- Topics
- Authors
- Journals
- Numbers
- Evolution
- Review
- Feedback

Papers

Analyzed 1000 papers and 9 topics.

Show all papers

Frequent words

active metabolic genetic study modeling
effective proteins adult
disease gene expressed animal
physiology associate
change relate celled increase
functional factor

Papers per year

Papers similarity

The graph below shows papers similarity network. Similar papers are located closely.

Edges represent co-citations, common references and citations between papers.

Color represents topic, size - total citations number.

Glyphosate

<http://maps.gargantext.org/phylo/glyphosate/paper08/>

PURE suggest

<https://fabian-beck.github.io/pure-suggest/>

Carto地理可视化: <https://carto.com/>

全球安全科学研究机构的分布

safety_institutions 1
Edit metadata...

DATA VIEW MAP VIEW

cartodb_id	the_geom	_end	altitudemode	begin	description	draworder	extrude	icon	name	tessellate	timestamp	visibl
number	geometry	date	string	date	string	number	number	string	string	number	date	numt
1	153.0128,-27.4978	null	null	null	Monash University, Australia	null	-1	null	Monash Univ	-1	null	-1
2	-83.7346,42.2756	null	null	null	University of Michigan, MI	null	-1	null	Univ Michigan	-1	null	-1
3	4.3693,52.0055	null	null	null	Delft University of Technology, Netherlands	null	-1	null	Delft Univ Technol	-1	null	-1
4	-96.3396,30.6128	null	null	null	Texas A&M University, TX	null	-1	null	Texas A&M Univ	-1	null	-1
5	-90.3013,38.6478	null	null	null	Washington University in St Louis, MO	null	-1	null	Univ Washington	-1	null	-1
6	151.2261,-33.9170	null	null	null	University of New South Wales, Australia	null	-1	null	Univ New S Wales	-1	null	-1
7	-164.8231,64.4505	null	null	null	Port Safety, AK	null	-1	null	Insurance Inst Highway Safety	-1	null	-1
8	21.8922,43.3204	null	null	null	Nis, Serbia	null	-1	null	NIOSH	-1	null	-1
9	5.6981,58.9371	null	null	null	University of Stavanger, Norway	null	-1	null	Univ Stavanger	-1	null	-1
10	-93.1260,40.2021	null	null	null	Milan, MO	null	-1	null	Politecn Milan	-1	null	-1
11	-76.9389,38.9878	null	null	null	University of Maryland, MD	null	-1	null	Univ Maryland	-1	null	-1
12	153.0239,-27.4667	null	null	null	The University of Queensland, Australia	null	-1	null	Queensland Univ Technol	-1	null	-1
13	-79.0301,35.9087	null	null	null	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, NC	null	-1	null	Univ N Carolina	-1	null	-1
14	151.1913,-33.8848	null	null	null	University of Technology, Australia	null	-1	null	Univ Sydney	-1	null	-1
15	-71.1233,42.3756	null	null	null	Harvard University, MA	null	-1	null	Harvard Univ	-1	null	-1
16	170.5112,-45.8669	null	null	null	Otago University, New Zealand	null	-1	null	Univ Otago	-1	null	-1
17	70.0000,40.0000	null	null	null	University of Toronto, ON	null	-1	null	Univ Toronto	-1	null	-1

scientopy

<https://www.scientopy.com/en/>

ScientoPy

1. Pre-processing 2. Analysis

ScientoPy

Universidad del Cauca, Popayán, Colombia
MIT License
Version 2.1.0

Dataset folder: Select dataset

Remove duplicated documents Open preprocess brief Run preprocess

biblioshiny: the shiny app for bibliometrix

<https://www.bibliometrix.org/>

biblioshiny: the shiny app for bibliometrix

Aria, M., & Cuccurullo, C. (2017). **bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis**. *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 959-975.

For an introduction and live examples, visit the [bibliometrix website](https://www.bibliometrix.org/).

Clustering by Coupling

Map Network Table Clusters

Run

Impact

Centrality

Cluster	Keywords	Confidence
Top-Right	science - conf 10%, citation perspective - conf 10%, creativity - conf 100%	100%
Top-Mid	science - conf 50%, networks - conf 55.6%, author cocitation - conf 66.7%	66.7%
Top-Center	emerging trends - conf 100%, patterns - conf 71.4%, cocitation - conf 77.8%	77.8%
Bottom-Left	hypertext - conf 100%, individual-differences - conf 100%, knowledge - conf 42.9%	100%
Bottom-Center	co-authorship - conf 66.7%, impact - conf 33.3%, patterns - conf 14.3%	66.7%
Bottom-Right	centrality - conf 50%, diversity - conf 100%, maps - conf 66.7%	100%

Options

Unit of Analysis: Documents

Parameters: -

Coupling measured by: References

Impact measure: Local Citation Score

Cluster labeling by: Keyword Plus

Number of Units: 250, Min Cluster Freq.: 5

Labels per cluster: 3, Label size: 0.3

文献引用网络图

<https://xg1990.com/citegraph/>

文献引用网络图

使用说明

重置

45%

停止布局运动[渲染提速]

YEAR:2006

鼠标所在论文id: 229:

标题: [The Real Virtuality of Metaverses](#)

作者: Schlemmer, E; Backes, L

发表时间: 2015

说明: [蓝色](#)代表被引论文, [绿色](#)代表引用论文; 论文排列从上到下, 从新到旧; 结点越大, 被引越多 | [知识共享许可协议](#) | 作者 xg1990 | 代码地址 <https://github.com/xg1990/citation-graph> | 基于 Bootstrap, arborjs 开发

文献计量在线分析平台 | 分析结果

(bibliometric.com)

Excellence Map

<https://www.excellencemapping.net/>

SciMAT

<https://sci2s.ugr.es/scimat>

Multi-RPYS

<http://www.leydesdorff.net/comins/rpys/index.html>

Multi-RPYS Heatmap (Rank Transformed)

Visualizing Referenced Publication Years by Publication Years of the Citing Documents

CitNetExplorer

<https://www.citnetexplorer.nl/>

HistCite

Pajek

<http://mrvar.fdv.uni-lj.si/pajek/>

Loet tools+Pajek

<http://www.leydesdorff.net/software/index.html>

Gephi <https://gephi.org>

Netdraw 网络分析软件

Ucinet

清林情报分析师软件(v6.0)

<http://qltek.com/#/screening>

项目管理

- 数据管理
- 项目搜索
- 数据导出
- 数据快照
- 关系设置
- 事件设置
- 地图设置

可视化应用

- 图布局
- 图样式
- 图对齐
- 图动画
- 图提取
- 图搜索
- 图过滤

可视化关系分析

- 时间分析
- 流向分析
- 集合分析
- 合计分析
- 路径分析
- 合并分析
- 资金穿透
- 拓展分析
- 图数关联

数据表分析

- 汇总分析
- 魔方分析
- 事件分析
- 待调单分析
- 地图分析
- 筛选分析
- 排序分析
- 资金报告
- 数据导出

数据处理

- 数据筛选
- SQL查询
- 隐藏空列
- 数据去重
- 自动补全
- 无效数据
- 插入新列
- 编辑数据

数据采集

- 数据导入
- 自动匹配
- 模板匹配
- 模板导入
- 历史打开
- 关系导入

© 清林情报分析师软件 v6.0

SPSS

Dendrogram using Average Linkage (Between Groups)
Rescaled Distance Cluster Combine

SATI

<http://sationline.cn/#!/read?jobId=20220801205212524-9d726b0c>

如您使用SATI软件进行研究，请引入如下一文：[刘启元,叶康.文献聚类信息挖掘技术方法及其软件SATI的实现——以中外图书情报学为例\[J\].信息资源管理学报,2012,\(01\):50-58.](#)

SATI 数据分析任务示例

期刊分析:《信息资源管理学报》

- EndNote_CNKI 格式 - 至05/2020
- 文献总数 498 | 作者 1073 | 关键词 2215 | 机构 689 | 发表年 10

主题分析:“知识图谱”主题高被引前1500篇文献

- EndNote_CNKI 格式 - 至05/2020
- 文献总数 498 | 来源 459 | 作者 3612 | 关键词 6571 | 机构 2079 | 发表年 22

引文分析: Informetrics 相关文章

- Text_WOS 格式 - 至06/2019
- 文献总数 100 | 来源 55 | 作者 249 | 关键词 396 | 引文 4128 | 发表年 4

SATI 可以做什么?

任务基础信息 Basics

频次/频率 Frequency

时间序列 Time Series

[关键词频次](#) [关键词频率](#)

[作者频次](#) [作者频率](#)

[机构频次](#) [机构频率](#)

[期刊频次](#) [期刊频率](#)

[引文频次](#) [引文频率](#)

知识图谱 Knowledge Graph

自动聚类 Clustering

条形竞赛动图 Bar Chart Race

作者 频率时间序列

注意: 频率 = 频次 / 当年总和 * 100。这里的[频次]是该词条在某年出现的次数; [频率]是该词条在某年出现次数占总词条数的百分比。

展示字段个数:33 (最大值:50)

显示标签: true

刷新

作者 频率时间序列

Jigsaw: Visual Analytics for Exploring and Understanding Document Collections

<https://www.cc.gatech.edu/gvu/ii/jigsaw/>

The screenshot displays the Jigsaw interface with three list views. The top navigation bar includes 'ListView', 'List Modes' (Any, All, Same, All-Any), 'Add new List', and 'Tutorial'. The 'Bachelors' list shows a scrollable list of universities, with 'Georgia Institute of Technolog...' highlighted in yellow. The 'Doctorate' list shows a similar list of universities, with 'Georgia Institute of Technolog...' highlighted in orange and a count of 10. The 'JoinYear' list shows a list of years, with '2008' highlighted in orange and a count of 3. Each list view includes a search bar and a set of icons for filtering and sorting.

A collage of four different visual analytics views from the Jigsaw interface. The top-left view shows a list of documents with columns for various attributes. The top-right view shows a network graph with nodes and edges. The bottom-left view shows a network graph with nodes and edges, similar to the top-right view. The bottom-right view shows a scatter plot with nodes and edges, similar to the top-right view.

Publish or Perish

Explains the use of Publish or Perish and its metrics

<https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>

The screenshot shows the Harzing's Publish or Perish (Windows GUI Edition) 8.2.3944.8118 interface. The main window displays search results for 'Moed, Henk F. - Visiting prof...'. The results table includes columns for Papers, Cites, Cites/y..., h, g, hI,norm..., hI,annual, hA, acc10, and Search date. The selected entry for 'Moed, Henk F.' shows 300 papers, 17032 cites, and a Cites/year of 436.72. The right-hand pane displays 'Citation metrics' for the selected entry, including Publication years (1983-2021), Citation years (39), Papers (300), Citations (17032), Cites/year (436.72), Cites/paper (56.77), Authors/paper (2.49), h-index (67), g-index (129), hI,norm (44), hI,annual (1.13), hA-index (17), and Papers with ACC >= 1,2,5,10,20 (133,102,61,32,15). Below the search results, there is a 'Google Scholar Profile search' section with a profile name 'Moed, Henk F. - Visiting professor, Sapienza Univ Rome; ex CWTS Leiden Univ, ex Elsevier' and a profile ID 'qgrbFW8AAAAJ'. The 'Annual citations' table shows data from 1991 to 2006. At the bottom, a list of papers is shown with columns for Cites, Per year, Rank, Authors, Title, and Year. The first paper is 'Citation analysis in research eva...' by HF Moed, published in 2005.

Citation metrics	Help	Cites	Per year	Rank	Authors
Publication years:	1983-2021	2111	124.18	1	HF Moed
Citation years:	39 (1983-2022)	746	62.17	2	HF Moed
Papers:	300	629	23.30	3	H Moed, R De Bruin, TH Van Leeuwen
Citations:	17032	614	16.59	4	HF Moed, WJM Burger, JG Frankfort, AFJ V
Cites/year:	436.72	536	17.29	5	RR Braam, HF Moed, AFJ Van Raan
Cites/paper:	56.77	503	23.95	6	T Van Leeuwen, H Moed, R Tijssen, M Visse
Authors/paper:	2.49	442	22.10	7	W Glänzel, HF Moed
h-index:	67	418	20.90	8	W Glänzel, HF Moed
g-index:	129	412	20.60	9	HF Moed
hI,norm:	44	411	31.62	10	HF Moed
hI,annual:	1.13	410	22.78	11	HF Moed, W Glänzel, U Schmoch
hA-index:	17	384	16.70	12	ECM Noyons, HF Moed, M Luwel
Papers with ACC >= 1,2,5,10,20:	133,102,61,32,15	327	12.11	13	HF Moed, TN Van Leeuwen
		302	9.74	14	RR Braam, HF Moed, AFJ Van Raan
		284	10.92	15	HF Moed, TN Van Leeuwen
		276	14.53	16	T Van Leeuwen, M Visser, H Moed, T Nede
		271	18.07	17	HF Moed
		236	47.20	18	G Halevi, H Moed, J Bar-Ilan
		235	16.79	19	HF Moed
		214	12.59	20	HF Moed
		214	10.70	21	H Moed
		196	14.00	22	C López-Illescas, F de Moya-Anegón, HF M

Knowledge Matrix plus

SCI of SCI

<https://sci2.cns.iu.edu/user/index.php>

The screenshot shows the Sci2 Tool interface with several panels:

- Console:** Displays log messages for various operations like 'Create an R Instance was selected' and 'Merge Node and Edge Files was selected'.
- Data Manager:** Shows a tree view of data processing steps, including 'ISI Data', '1652 Unique ISI Records', 'Co-Word Occurrence network', and 'Standardized Journal Names'.
- Scheduler:** A table showing the progress of various algorithms.
- Workflow Manager:** A visual representation of the data processing workflow.

Algorithm Name	Date	Time	% Complete
✓ Merge Node and Ed...	03/31/2016	11:44:27 AM	100%
✓ Multipartite Joining	03/31/2016	11:36:16 AM	100%
✓ Create an R Instance	03/31/2016	11:35:54 AM	100%
✓ GUESS	03/31/2016	11:32:13 AM	100%
✓ Detect Duplicate Nod...	03/31/2016	11:30:59 AM	100%
✓ Detect Duplicate Nod...	03/31/2016	11:29:20 AM	100%

© 2008 The Regents of the University of California and SciTech Strategies.
Map updated by SciTech Strategies, OST, and CNS in 2011.

Legend

Circle area: Fractional record count
 Unclassified = 114
 Minimum = 0
 Maximum = 39
 Color: Discipline
 See end of PDF for color legend.

Scholar Tree

<http://tlfung.cs.ucdavis.edu:7070/>

Stick: Paper

Trunk Side: Conference paper (left)

Branches: Published year

Branch Interval: 1234567 years

Branch Side: First authored papers (lower side)

Fruit: Paper length (> 4 pages)

Leaf: Co-author

Leaf Color: First co-authored year

Leaf Size: Total co-authored papers

Leaf Color Legend:

	< 1997
	< 2000
	< 2003
	< 2006
	< 2009
	< 2012
	<= 2015

T. -L. Fung, J. -K. Chou and K. -L. Ma, "A design study of personal bibliographic data visualization," 2016 IEEE Pacific Visualization Symposium (PacificVis), 2016, pp. 244-248, doi: 10.1109/PACIFICVIS.2016.7465279.

Muxviz (R 多层网络分析)

<https://manlius.github.io/muxViz/>

File ▾ Diagnostics Visualization Reducibility Motifs Dynamics Data Help ▾

MUX VIZ

Multilayer
Correlations

Multilayer
Versatility

Multilayer
Community

Multilayer
Reducibility

Multilayer
Motifs

Multivariate
Analysis

Geographical
Embedding

muxViz Version: 0.3.0

Last update: 2 Jul 2015

System: Darwin

Darwin Kernel Version 13.2.0: Thu Apr 17
23:03:13 PDT 2014; root:xnu-
2422.100.13~1/RELEASE_X86_64

R version 3.2.0 (2015-04-16)

✓ Octave found.
✓ Fanmod found.

Paperpoles

<http://www.jianguenhe.com/paperpoles/>

Visual Exploration Data Visualization Visual Interfaces

Visualizing Kno
reference citation

CiteSpace II: D
reference citation

+

Mapping the ✕

查看原图

Sort by Relevance

La visualización de la información en el entorno de la Ciencia de la Informació
Cited by 1 Deborah Torres Ponjuan (2011)
☆ BOOKMARK DELETE LIKE UNLIKE ABSTRAC

Information retrieval across information visualization
Cited by 1 Veslava Osinska, Piotr Bala,... Federated Conference on Computer Scie... (20
☆ BOOKMARK DELETE LIKE UNLIKE ABSTRAC

Exploitation of information resources within knowledge society: digital library
Cited by 2 Angela Repanovici (2006)
☆ BOOKMARK DELETE LIKE UNLIKE ABSTRAC

Thinking inside the box? Intellectual structure of the knowledge base of innovation research (1988–2008)
Cited by 92 Muhammad Shafique Strategic Management Journal (2013)
☆ BOOKMARK DELETE LIKE UNLIKE ABSTRAC

Knowledge mapping of the Iranian nanoscience and technology: a text mining approach
Cited by 8 Ehsan Mohammadi Scientometrics (2012)
☆ BOOKMARK DELETE LIKE UNLIKE ABSTRAC

Author Co-Citation Analysis (ACA): a powerful tool for representing implicit knowledge of scholar knowledge workers
Cited by 0 Rasoul Zavaqaj (2010)
☆ BOOKMARK DELETE LIKE UNLIKE ABSTRAC

Mapping Medline papers, genes, and proteins related to melanoma research
Cited by 14 Kevin W Boyack, Ketan K Mane, Katy Borner (2004)

He, J., Ping, Q., Lou, W. and Chen, C. (2019), PaperPoles: Facilitating adaptive visual exploration of scientific publications by citation links. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 70: 843-857. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24171>

VxInsight

https://www.arabidopsis.org/download/index-auto.jsp?dir=%2Fdownload_files%2FSoftware%2FVxInsight

Davidson G S , Hendrickson B , Johnson D K , et al. Knowledge Mining With VxInsight: Discovery Through Interaction[J]. Journal of Intelligent Information Systems, 1998, 11(3):259-285.

covariate

<https://covariate.com/search>

Tree of Science ToS

<https://coreofscience.shinyapps.io/scientometrics/>

Core of science

Choose .bib File

Browse... No file selected

Introduction

Importance

Evolution - ToS

Subfields

Introduction

Tree of Science ToS

Tree of Science (ToS) is a Web based tool for scientific articles selection. ToS was created in order to solve the difficulties to find relevant articles in a research topics and to make easier the process on writing the theoretical framework. ToS has three advantages: decreases the time interval bias in the search, decreases bias of the databases indexed in the search, diminishes the rigor of keywords. ToS is directed to all

Subfields

Evolution ToS

Choose a subfield group

CR_AUTHOR	CR_TITLE	CR_YEAR	group	link
1. SHISSICOLLARD, E., LELL, A., ZITL, W.,	MAPPING NANOSCIENCES BY CITATION FLOWS: A PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS	2017	Group 1	https://www.google.com/search?q=mapping+nanosciences+by+citation+flows+a+preliminary+analysis
2. SINGH, N. K.,	AUTHORSHIP PATTERN AND COLLABORATION COEFFICIENT OF INDIA IN BIOTECHNOLOGY RESEARCH DURING 2003-2016: BASED ON SCOPUS DATABASE	2017	Group 1	https://www.google.com/search?q=authorship+pattern+and+collaboration+coefficient+of+india+in+biotechnology+research+during+2003-2016+based+on+scopus+database
3. SHANKAR, R., SIKHATHI, R.,	MODIFIED COLLABORATIVE COEFFICIENT: A NEW MEASURE FOR QUANTIFYING THE DEGREE OF RESEARCH COLLABORATION	2013	Group 1	https://www.google.com/search?q=modified+collaborative+coefficient+a+new+measure+for+quantifying+the+degree+of+research+collaboration

Wordcloud

Minimum Frequency: 10

Maximum Number of Words: 100

Select words to remove

Print Download wordcloud

Tree of Science (ToS) is a Web based tool for scientific articles selection. ToS was created in order to solve the difficulties to find relevant articles in a research topics and to make easier the process on writing the theoretical framework. ToS has three advantages: decreases the time interval bias in the search, decreases bias of the databases indexed in the search, diminishes the rigor of keywords. ToS is directed to all academic community and researchers, and students completing a short-term research project. ToS philosophy has been based on three pillars: simplicity, effectiveness and innovation. Simplicity is based on organic concepts to help the user understanding about the structure of science from the tree metaphor. The effectiveness is based on the accuracy of the results of scientific articles. Finally, innovation part of a continuous improvement of the services provided so ToS can surprise the users.

ITGInsight

<http://cn.itginsight.com/>

ITGInsight1.6.0

BiblioTools / BiblioMaps

<http://www.sebastian-grauwin.com/bibliomaps/>

PROJECTNAME Corpus Description BC Clusters About

Thematic Map

Based on the references they share, 10440 thematically close publications of the studied corpus are gathered into 32 topics (Q=0.87) and 224 subtopics (Q=0.689). For methodological details and tutorials, refer to the [About the project](#) page.

Legend Search Layout Export

- Circles represent research topics. Circle size is proportional to the number of publications in a topic.
- Lines represent connections between topics. Line thickness is proportional to the similarity of two topics.
- Colors represent inclusions within a research topic.

XY Labels correspond to:

Select Level: Topics Subtopics

Select Layout: Static Dynamic

LONG-RANGE INTERACTIONS
The topic LONG-RANGE INTERACTIONS gathers 159 publications.

Compared to the average trend, the number of publication in a given year can be: significantly less than expected, as expected, or significantly more than expected.

Jump to:

Most Frequent Keywords

Keyword	f(%)	σ
DYNAMICS	15.72	+
STATISTICAL-MECHANICS	11.95	++
MODEL	11.32	+
FLOW	10.06	+
SYSTEMS	10.06	+
STABILITY	9.43	+
TURBULENCE	9.43	+

PROJECTNAME Corpus Description BC Clusters About

Thematic Map

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- Colors represent inclusions within a research topic.

XY Labels correspond to:

Select Level: Topics Subtopics

Select Layout: Static Dynamic

CoPalRed

战略坐标图

IN-SPIRE™ Visual Document Analysis

<https://in-spire.pnnl.gov/>

IN-SPIRE
Explore and Discover!
Automatic Topic Discovery,
Visualization and Analysis

Discover Trends Over Time

Organize Your Documents

View Documents and Terms of Interest

"Slice and Dice" Your Categorical Fields

See Your Information Landscape

Pacific Northwest
NATIONAL LABORATORY
Proudly Operated by Battelle Since 1965

IN-SPIRE 4.6 - Google "chicken"

File Tools Viewpoints Translation Help

Galaxy - Google "chicken"

File View Tools Capture

0 total selected

Peak Labels

Number of Labels: 17

Number of Words Per Label: 3

OK Cancel

meat, recipes, recipe
recipe, thanks, love
wings, recipes, cooking
meat, cooking, recipes
comment, posted, dor
meat, foods, chickens
robot, tv, season
posted, love, life
comment, tv, review
pox, health, children
chickens, re, life
chickens, eggs, egg
space, invaders, download
chickens, eggs, egg
gene, genome, gallus
genome, human, university

Outliers Recalculate Shortcuts

Outlier Terms

Select: Click or drag to select docs; Shift-click or drag to add to current selection; Alt-click or drag to remove from selection; Shift-Alt-click or drag to select just colored docs.

<https://in-spire.pnnl.gov/videos/#ExploringData>

Infomap **Network Navigator** Interactive hierarchical network navigator

<https://www.mapequation.org/navigator/>

Infomap Network Navigator

Hide sidebar

Find nodes...

Selected module

Name	2295 ASTROPHYS J, 12634 PHYS R
Tree path	root
Flow	1,000
In degree	0
Out degree	0
Nodes	11
Links	40
Leaf nodes	12957

Flow distribution

Linear Log

Degree distribution

Occurrences

File	Nodes	Color
No files loaded		

+ Add file

<https://www.mapequation.org/assets/publications/RosvallBergstromPNAS2008Full.pdf>

野村総合研究所(NRI)について

<http://www.trueteller.net/patent/patent.html>

図表1 リチウムイオン電池に関する分析例

単語マップ (下敷き)
(単語に付与した「属性」によるグルーピング)

A社 被引用数で重み付け
(プロットは被引用数 ≥ 10 の文献)

A社 単純件数

A社-B社
(緑～水色：A社が出願多、
紺～黒：B社が出願多の領域)

Konica

Minolta

Derwent Data Analyzer

<https://www.thevantagepoint.com/tda-home.html>

Data Viz Project | Collection of data visualizations to get inspired and find the right type.

DPV ALL FAMILY INPUT FUNCTION SHAPE Q i by **ferdio** hire us!

A	X	Y
60%	0-2	30
	2-4	34
	4-6	38

Event	Time
A	1-4-2015
B	10-4-2015
C	12-4-2015

Location	Value
A	5
B	30
C	15

Age	F	M
10-20	30	28
20-30	34	22
30-40	38	26

X	Y	Z
1	30	10
2	34	14
3	38	12

X	Y	Z	
A	12	34	26
B	4	20	28

Start	200
A	+50
B	-20

A	A ₁	14
A	A ₂	16
B	B ₁	10

A	B	C
A	1	1
B	1	0
C	0	0

X	Y
A	30% 28%
B	34% 38%
C	26% 24%

Matrix Diagram (Roof Shaped)

Matrix Diagram

	1	2	3
A	●		●
B		○	●
C	○		

Sociogram

Network Visualisation

Connection Map

Matrix Diagram (Y-Shaped)

Non-ribbon Chord Diagram

Molecule Diagram

CN1C=NC2=C1C(=O)N(C)C2=O

Radial Convergences

rgee + rayshader integration and R spatial ecosystem in 3D visualization topics/subjects

<https://github.com/ambarja/rgee3D>

Population density 2020

Origin

<https://wordsift.org/>

Orbit专利分析

<https://www.questel.com/ip-intelligence-software/orbit-intelligence/>

<https://www.wizard.ai/>

<https://icite.od.nih.gov/analysis>

Results for patient safety

[Citing Papers](#) [Referenced Papers](#)

Not all requested data was found. [View details](#)

[Influence](#) [Translation](#) [Citations](#)

Total Pubs	Pubs Per Year	Avg. Human	Avg. Animal	Avg. Mol/Cell	Median RCR	Avg. APT	Cited By Clin.
9962	3320.67	0.90	0.02	0.06	2.40	10.6%	140

[Influence](#) [Translation](#) [Citations](#)

Roll over table headers for definitions; visit the [Global RCR Stats](#) page for percentile tables

Total Pubs	Pubs Per Year	Cites Per Year				Relative Citation Ratio (RCR)				Weighted RCR
		MAX	MEAN	SEM	MED	MAX	MEAN	SEM	MED	
7789	3894.50	39.00	0.33	0.01	0.00	3.51	2.40	0.56	1.85	7.20

http://oskg.whu.edu.cn/Web_NEviewer/index.html

- NEViewer-online: 复杂网络演化分析与趋势探测在线服务平台 (qq.com)

Free topic extraction tool for documents and social media

<https://nocodefunctions.com/topics/topic-extraction-tool.html?lang=en>

feedback English Nocode functions Menu

Free topic extraction tool for documents and social media

Use it directly by selecting the data to be analyzed:

Plain text (txt or pdf files)

or

Structured text in columns or tables (csv or Excel files)

or

Search and import tweets

... or read below about what it does, and how it works:

Topic extraction - automate the analysis of key topics in your texts

This function identifies automatically the key topics in a text, an operation called **topic extraction** or **topic modelling**. It analyzes the text line by line and determines groups of words and expressions which tend to **cluster** together, forming topics. It works on texts written in a large variety of languages (including texts in non Latin alphabet). The function follows the principles of unsupervised learning, which is a type of **machine learning**.

1 import this text

Example: ~ 3000 tweets by Donald Trump and Hillary Clinton as a text file, available on Kaggle
<https://www.kaggle.com/benhamner/clinton-trump-tweets/home>

Extract:

Great poll Florida - thank you!
 Thank you Ohio - see you tonight!
 Why isn't President Obama working instead of campaigning for Hillary Clinton?
 "You don't grade the presidency on a curve." —@POTUS
 Thank you Rep. @CynthiaLummis!
 CHILD CARE REFORMS THAT WILL MAKE AMERICA GREAT AGAIN!
 Student debt and the cost of college are incredibly important.
 Debt shouldn't hold people back from going to college.
 Trump's calling for trillion dollar tax cuts for Wall Street.
 Trump University students entrusted Trump with their futures, and he scammed them.
 "@tcloer11: @realDonaldTrump Great job! Make America Great Again!"

2 export the results

In one click, a list of topics is identified (only the first 6 topics are shown here). Download the Excel file with all the key terms.

topics	key terms
topic 0	drug x 12, price x 8
topic 1	club x 16, growth x 13
topic 2	bernie x 81, deal x 67, voter x 57, supporter x 52, dem x 31, trade x 29, energy x 29, rigged x 28, badly x 27, tim x 25
topic 3	businesses x 21, stif x 5
topic 4	nydailynew x 8, zuckerman x 7
topic 5	trump x 1264, america x 415, nation x 48, stronger x 44, city x 40, washington x 32, message x 30, hope x 29, hurt x 26, california x 25
topic 6	obamacare x 15, repeal x 12, healthcare x 6

EMOTE—a database of 26 (and growing!) experience-sampling data sets measuring emotions in everyday life

The image shows the top section of the EMOTE website. At the top left is the logo "EMOTE" with the tagline "Everyday Measures Of Temporal Emotions". To the right of the logo is a navigation menu with links: "About", "Datasets", "Constructs", "Request data", "Share data", "FAQ", "Contact", and "Login". Below the navigation is a large banner image of a busy pedestrian crosswalk. Overlaid on the left side of the banner is a dark grey box containing the "EMOTE" logo in large white letters, the tagline "Everyday Measures Of Temporal Emotions", and a search bar with the text "Search this site" and a "SEARCH" button.

<https://emotedatabase.com/constructs/network/>

CHI2022 Tweets Network

<https://observablehq.com/@john-guerra/chi2022-tweets-network>

John Alexis Guerra Gómez · johnguerra.co
I love to build dataviz for insight discovery. I also love to put technology to the service of humanity

Published May 5 Fork of IEEEVIS Tweets Network All Data

CHI2022 Tweets Network

Here are 11605 CHI2022 tweets collected from Mon May 02 2022 07:54:08 GMT+0800 (中国标准时间) until Mon May 09 2022 07:54:08 GMT+0800 (中国标准时间) that were used to create my [analysis of the most influentials accounts for CHI2022](#)

Each dot is a tweet, there are links for reweets, quotes and replies (haven't figured out favorites yet). Circle area is the favorite count. Check the controls below to manipulate parameters. Color shows the users with most favorites overall. Click to see a tweet below.

```
md`  
  
Here are nodes.length CHI2022 tweets collected from x.domain()[0] until  
x.domain()[1]  
} that were used to create my [analysis of the most influentials accounts for CHI2022](http://johnguerra.co/viz/influentials/story/?hashtag=chi2022)  
  
Each dot is a tweet, there are links for reweets, quotes and replies (haven't figured out favorites yet). Circle area is the favorite count. Check the controls below to manipulate parameters. Color shows the users with most favorites overall. Click to see a tweet below.
```

Mon 02 12 PM Tue 03 12 PM Wed 04 12 PM Thu 05 12 PM Fri 06 12 PM Sat 07 12 PM May 08 12 PM

<http://well-formed.eigenfactor.org/radial.html>

<https://voyant-tools.org/>

<http://www.statsilk.com/>

Local-Citation-Network:

<https://timwoelfle.github.io/Local-Citation-Network/>

Local Citation Network beta Eck 2010 (OA) ✕

Input articles (32) Incoming suggestions (▲ 10)

Based on the references of the following source article (★) (link to share):

Nees Jan van Eck, Ludo Waltman, *Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping*, Scientometrics, 2010. (select)

Data retrieved through OpenAlex (OA) API on 2022/9/4 (estimated completeness: 90%).

Title & Abstract	Filter articles...	32 / 32				
Title	First Author	Year	Cit	InDeg	OutDeg	Ref
> Visualizing knowledge domains	Borner	2005	947	7	2	175
> An algorithm for drawing general undirected graphs	Kamada	1989	2133	7	0	17
> Co-word maps of biotechnology: An example of cognitive scientometrics	Rip	1984	227	6	0	8
> Mapping the backbone of science	Boyack	2005	648	6	0	0
> Graph drawing by force-directed placement	Fruchterman	1991	3758	6	1	8
> Clustering the science citation index ® using co-citations	Small	1985	270	5	0	8
> Co-word-based science maps of chemical engineering. Part I: Representations by direct multidimensional scaling	Peters	1993	173	4	1	18
> Requirements for a cocitation similarity measure, with special reference to Pearson's correlation coefficient	Ahlgren	2003	513	4	0	34
> Cluster stability and the use of noise in interpretation of clustering	Davidson	2001	71	3	2	18
> Pathfinder networks and author cocitation analysis: a remapping of paradigmatic information scientists	White	2003	237	3	1	38
> Clusters and maps of science journals based on bi-connected graphs in Journal Citation Reports	Leydesdorff	2004	96	3	4	46
> BIBLIOMETRIC MAPPING OF THE COMPUTATIONAL INTELLIGENCE FIELD	Eck	2007	147	3	4	14
> Multivariate Density Estimation	Scott	1992	2776	2	0	0
> Shadows of the Past in International Cooperation: Collaboration Profiles of the Top Five Producers of Science	Zitt	2000	192	2	0	39
> Quantitative evaluation of large maps of science	Klavans	2006	70	2	4	17
> VOS: A New Method for Visualizing Similarities between Objects	Eck	2007	170	2	0	8
> Science and technology mapping: A new iteration model for representing multidimensional relationships	Kopcsa	1998	8	2	1	8
> Visualizing the marrow of science	Moya-Anegón	2007	22	2	6	25
> Identifying a better measure of relatedness for mapping science	Klavans	2005	22	2	2	32
> GraphSplatting: visualizing graphs as continuous fields	Liere	2003	66	1	0	11
> Graph theoretic foundations of pathfinder networks	Schvaneveldt	1988	78	1	0	35
> The world of geography: Visualizing a knowledge domain with cartographic means	Skupin	2004	101	1	1	5

Citation network Co-authorship network

(fullscreen network)

1 newer articles

(how to read this network)

1 older articles

<https://compas.kisti.re.kr/index.jsp>

Search US Patent	Search US Patent Assignment		
 Trade Scan <i>Import & export statistics</i>			
 Journal Article Analysis <i>Research trend analysis based on journal articles</i>			
 Tech Path <i>How far can you reach?</i>			
 Korean Patent Analysis <i>Research trend analysis based on patents</i>			
 COMPAS Manual			

Scholarcy

Connecting the dots: knowledge graphs for all

← medRxiv neurology Log out

My Libraries > RSS Feeds > medRxiv neurology

Search document or library

Move/Export/Delete Import

Articles (28)

Reorder articles Create folder

Title	Author	Headline	Added	Year	Citation	
CD19+ B cell numbers predict the increase of anti-SARS CoV2 antibodies in fingolimod-treated and COVID-19-vaccinated patients with multiple sclerosis	Schiavetti, I., Barcellini, L., Lapucci, C.	The results of this study demonstrate that the number and proportion of peripheral blood CD19+ B lymphocytes before the third dose of COVID-19 vaccination, in patients treated with fingolimod, predict the subsequent increase of anti-SARS CoV2 antibodies	26.07.2022	2022	0	
Deep profiling of multiple ischemic lesions in a large, multi-center cohort: Frequency, spatial distribution, and associations to clinical characteristics	Bonkhoff, A., Ullberg, T., Bretzner, M.	Multiple lesions were distinctly linked to a higher acute stroke severity, a higher diffusion-weighted imaging lesion volume and lower WMH lesion volume	26.07.2022	2022	0	
Monoallelic CRMP1 gene variants cause neurodevelopmental disorder	Ravindran, E., Arashiki, N., Becker, L.-L.	We report the human phenotype associated with heterozygous CRMP1 variants in three affected children of unrelated non-consanguineous pedigrees	26.07.2022	2022	0	

Markdown Export selected

Default - Obsidian v0.14.2

Graph view

Filters

Search files...

Tags

Attachments

Existing files only

Orphans

Groups

New group

Display

Arrows

Text fade threshold

Node size

Link thickness

Animate

Forces

Center force

Repel force

Link force

Link distance

#parkinson_disease

Cosmograph: <https://cosmograph.app/>

seaborn: statistical data visualization#

<http://seaborn.pydata.org/>

[Installing](#) [Gallery](#) [Tutorial](#) [API](#) [Releases](#) [Citing](#) [FAQ](#)

seaborn: statistical data visualization

Seaborn is a Python data visualization library based on `matplotlib`. It provides a high-level interface for drawing attractive and informative statistical graphics.

For a brief introduction to the ideas behind the library, you can read the [introductory notes](#) or the [paper](#). Visit the [installation page](#) to see how you can download the package and get started with it. You can browse the [example gallery](#) to see some of the things that you can do with seaborn, and then check out the [tutorials](#) or [API reference](#) to find out how.

To see the code or report a bug, please visit the [GitHub repository](#). General support questions are most at home on [stackoverflow](#), which has a dedicated channel for seaborn.

Contents

- [Installing](#)
- [Gallery](#)
- [Tutorial](#)
- [API](#)
- [Releases](#)
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- [FAQ](#)

Features

- New** [Objects: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Relational plots: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Distribution plots: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Categorical plots: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Regression plots: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Multi-plot grids: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Figure theming: API | Tutorial](#)
- [Color palettes: API | Tutorial](#)

KnowSDGs web platform

	No poverty
	Zero hunger
	Good health and well-being
	Quality education
	Gender equality
	Clean water and sanitation
	Affordable and clean energy
	Decent work and economic growth
	Industry, innovation and infrastructure
	Reduced inequalities
	Sustainable cities and communities
	Responsible consumption and production
	Climate action
	Life below water
	Life on land
	Peace, justice and strong institutions
	Partnerships for the goals

SDG POLICY MAPPING	SDG MAPPER TOOL	EC MODELS FOR SDGs	SDG INTERLINKAGES
ENABLINGS DGs TOOL	CONSUMER FOOTPRINT CALCULATOR	LOCALISING SDGs	SMART SPECIALISATION FOR SDGs

<https://knowsdgs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sdgmapper>

Nobel Prize: nominees and recipients. 1901–1964*

<https://ria.ru/20151210/1339535142.html?lang=en>

Literature

Great Britain 1912 r.

Number and breakdown of nominees this year:

Thomas Hardy.....	3
James G Frazer.....	2
George Bernard Shaw.....	1

Click on country to see how many times each national candidate was nominated for the Nobel Prize

63 years of Nobel Prize nominations

"It is my express wish that in awarding the prizes no consideration whatever shall be given to the nationality of the candidates, but that the most worthy shall receive the prize, whether he be a Scandinavian or not."

Paris, November 27, 1895
The will of Alfred Bernhard Nobel

Each year, about 300 eligible candidates are nominated for the Nobel Prize. Each candidate can be nominated more than once, but regardless, the Nobel Committee selects the winners.

Our infographic lists all Nobel Prize nominees from 1901-1963

BEGIN >

PubMed Mapping Tester

<https://esperr.github.io/mapping-tester/>

PubMed Mapping Tester

Why PubMed Mapping Tester?

With [Automatic Term Mapping](#), a simple text query is translated to a more complex one, often composed of [MeSH headings](#) as well as different text fields. The algorithm for doing so is maintained by the National Library of Medicine, and the final translation for a given search is viewable by selecting the "Advanced" tab in PubMed. To take one completely random example, the mapping for the term "covid-19" becomes this:

```
"covid 19"[All Fields] OR "covid 19"[MeSH Terms] OR "covid 19 vaccines"[All Fields] OR "covid 19 vaccines"[MeSH Terms] OR "covid 19 serotherapy"[All Fields] OR "covid 19 serotherapy"[Supplementary Concept] OR "covid 19 nucleic acid testing"[All Fields] OR "covid 19 nucleic acid testing"[MeSH Terms] OR "covid 19 serological testing"[All Fields] OR "covid 19 serological testing"[MeSH Terms] OR "covid 19 testing"[All Fields] OR "covid 19 testing"[MeSH Terms] OR "sars cov 2"[All Fields] OR "sars cov 2"[MeSH Terms] OR "severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2"[All Fields] OR "ncov"[All Fields] OR "2019 ncov"[All Fields] OR (("coronavirus"[MeSH Terms] OR "coronavirus"[All Fields] OR "cov"[All Fields]) AND 2019/11/01:3000/12/31[Date - Publication])
```

The other way to see the results of a search (and the mapping from which it is derived) is by using the API maintained by the NCBI. While the new version of PubMed has been in production for some months, the public API still points to the old search interface (and thus, the older iteration of ATM).

How does it work?

Happily, there is now a test instance of the API that points to the new search interface, allowing us to directly compare one version to the other (for at least the next several weeks before the old API is retired). It is these two different APIs that PubMed Mapping Tester uses to retrieve the two sets of results for comparison.

Te

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Res
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<https://ouestware.gitlab.io/retina/beta/>

beta

Retina

Retina is a web application that helps you share your graph visualizations online.

It currently accepts GEXF and GraphML files.

Your graph file is...

☁ Online

💻 On your computer

⏪ Edit Explore 🏠

⚙️ Graph visualization edition

Before sharing your graph online, you can first select various options on how users will **read and interrogate** this graph.

Your choices in this panel will impact the next white panel, which is the interface your users will have access to.

Once you are satisfied with your choices, click the [Share](#) button to **share or embed** this graph.

Which fields should be actionable?

Filter	Colors	Sizes	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tag
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	URL
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Cluster
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Score
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Degree
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Allow using default graph file colors and/or sizes

Which node information should show up on hovered nodes?

Select fields... ▾

How should the edges be colored?

Amanogawa

<https://lifescience.fronteo.com/aidiscovery/amanogawa>

<https://lifescience.fronteo.com/aidiscovery/amanogawa/>

<https://pypi.org/project/sviewgui/>

New version 1.0 of sviewgui is now released(<https://pypi.org/project/sviewgui/>) with a revised GUI design. (GUI for data visualization based on @matplotlib). A lot of new features are available (e.g. the log-scale plot with negative values, log histogram, kdeplot).

The Open Research Knowledge Graph aims to describe research papers in a structured manner

The screenshot shows the ORKG homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ORKG logo, menu items (View, Tools, About), a user profile (NFDI4DataScience), a search bar containing 'safety', and buttons for '+ Add new' and 'Sign in'. The main heading is 'Scholarly Knowledge. Comparable.' followed by a sub-heading: 'The Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) aims to describe research papers in a structured manner. With the ORKG, papers are easier to find and compare. Play video'. Below this is a 'Browse by research field' section with five red buttons: 'Arts and Humanities (90 papers)', 'Engineering (1417 papers)', 'Life Sciences (3366 papers)', 'Physical Sciences & Mathematics (2984 papers)', and 'Social and Behavioral Sciences (687 papers)'. The main content area is divided into 'Comparisons', 'Visualizations', and 'Papers'. The 'Comparisons' tab is active, showing a list of comparison entries. The first entry is 'Code-switched corpora for Named Entity Recognition (NER)' with 7 contributions and 0 visualizations, dated 07-09-2022. The second entry is 'Tailored Forming Processes for Manufacturing of Components with Bearing Raceways Using Different Material Combinations'. To the right, there is a blue 'Load timeline' button with a note about cookie guidelines, a 'Join ORKG!' section with a 'Sign up' button, and a 'Get cited' section with a quote icon and text about citation.

The screenshot shows a detailed comparison page in ORKG. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home >> Engineering >> Civil and Environmental Engineering >> Civil Engineering'. The page title is 'Comparison | 4 contributions'. There are buttons for '+ Add contribution', 'Visualize', and 'Actions'. A light blue tooltip says 'Use Shift + Mouse Wheel for horizontal scrolling in the table.' Below this is a table with five columns. The first column is 'Properties' with a dropdown menu showing 'research_problem'. The other four columns represent different contributions, each with a title, date, and a summary of its limitations or characteristics.

Properties	Earthquake Hazard Safety Assessment of Existing Buildings Using Optimized Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network 2020 - Contribution 1	Uncertainty and Fuzzy Decisions in Earthquake Risk Evaluation of Buildings 2019 - Contribution 1	Rapid visual screening procedure of existing building based on statistical analysis 2018 - Contribution 1	Differences in perception of indoor environment between Japanese and non-Japanese workers 2002 - Contribution 1
research_problem	limited to data, deal with non-linear relationships between inputs and output, speed in calculation	Limited to rules, complicated in calculation and needs lots of rules, good in dealing non-linear relationships of inputs and output	Limited to data, not properly dealing with non-linear relationships between inputs and outputs, limited and complicated to add extra inputs	Factors influencing human comfort

XML a EXCEL

<https://cdkm.com/es/xml-to-xls>

XML a EXCEL

Convertir XML a EXCEL en línea gratis

1 2 3
1: Elija varios archivos XML locales o ingrese la URL del archivo XML en línea. 2: Elija "EXCEL" como formato de destino y configure las opciones. 3: Haga clic en el botón "INICIAR CONVERSIÓN" para convertir XML a EXCEL en línea.

 ELIJA ARCHIVOS

Elija archivos o ingrese la URL del archivo remoto

FORMATO DE DESTINO:

XLS

 Establecer opciones de conversión (opcional)

 INICIAR CONVERSIÓN

Acepto términos y privacidad

ARCHIVOS DE SALIDA

 Comprimir archivos

 Borrar archivos

#	ARCHIVOS DE SALIDA	TAMAÑO DE ARCHIVO	DESCARGAR
---	--------------------	-------------------	-----------

XML
Extensible Markup Language

Extensión de archivo: .xml

XML, siglas en inglés de eXtensible Markup Language, traducido como "Lenguaje de Marcado Extensible" o "Lenguaje de Marcas Extensible", es un meta-lenguaje que permite definir lenguajes de marcas desarrollado por el World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) utilizado para almacenar datos en forma legible. Proviene del lenguaje SGML y permite definir la gramática de lenguajes específicos para estructurar documentos grandes.

EXCEL
Microsoft Excel Binary File Format

Extensión de archivo: .xls

La extensión de archivo por defecto del formato Excel puede ser .xls en versiones anteriores o iguales a Excel 2003 (11.0), .xlsx para libros de Excel regulares en versiones posteriores o iguales a Excel 2007 (12.0).

Based on the new classification of PubMed I have also created a map displaying all publications in PubMed for the last 2-years period.

<https://petersjogarde.github.io/papers/hiervis/bas/e/index.html>

LinkBERT: A Knowledgeable Language Model Pretrained with Document Links

<https://github.com/michiyasunaga/LinkBERT>

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository page for LinkBERT. At the top, there are navigation tabs for Projects, Security, and Insights. Below that, the repository name 'michiyasunaga/readme' is displayed along with commit information (210bc47 on 6 Apr, 2 commits). A list of files and folders is shown, including 'figs', 'scripts', 'src', '.gitignore', 'LICENSE', and 'README.md'. The 'README.md' file is selected, showing its content. The title 'LinkBERT: A Knowledgeable Language Model Pretrained with Document Links' is prominently displayed. Below the title, there are badges for 'PRs welcome', 'arXiv 2203.15827', and 'State of the Art' for 'Question Answering on MRQA' and 'Text Classification on BLURB'. A paragraph of text describes the repository's purpose: 'This repo provides the model, code & data of our paper: LinkBERT: Pretraining Language Models with Document Links (ACL 2022). [PDF] [HuggingFace Models]'. An 'Overview' section is also visible.

LinkBERT: Overview

Corpus of linked documents

Pretrain the LM

bibfix

<https://estech.shinyapps.io/bibfix/>

bibfix

Welcome to bibfix!

bibfix helps you to repair your bibliographic data files!

Upload an RIS file below to check its health and repair missing fields.

RIS file upload

Browse...

No file selected

<https://discovertext.com/>

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About our text analysis data science software

Collaborative text analytics for human and machine-learning

We provide dozens of multilingual, text mining, data science, human annotation, and machine-learning features.

DiscoverText offers a range of simple to advanced cloud-based software tools empowering users to quickly and accurately evaluate large amounts of text data. Our users work via a point and click graphical user interface in web browsers to sort unstructured free text common in market research, as well as associated metadata, also found in customer feedback platforms, CRMs, chats, email, large scale HR or other open-ended answers on surveys, [public comment to government agencies](#), Twitter, RSS feeds, and other forms of text data. DiscoverText is GSA-approved small business. [Students and professors get free access, training, and project support](#) directly from [the founder](#). Read more than [100 authenticated Capterra reviews](#) to find out [why we are ranked #1](#) by Predictive Analytics Today for text, metadata, and Twitter data analysis and trusted by hundreds of academic research groups.

Collect, clean, and analyze text data

Unstructured text data is messy

Data scientists working on text analytics and machine-learning know cleaning data can be time consuming. Users of DiscoverText build [reusable custom machine classifiers or "sifters"](#) to find the most (or least) relevant items before using other classifiers for sorting items into topic, sentiment, and other categories. DiscoverText combines hybrid data science methods (ex., crowdsourcing, measurement, adjudication, iteration, replication, annotator ranking) along with established e-discovery text analytics tools, to [shorten a process that used to last weeks or months when words get sorted in spreadsheets](#). Our machine-learning sifters are created in hours or just a few minutes using crowdsourcing. We offer an API and support technical integration with Twitter. [Academics trust DiscoverText to help them do better and more transparent scientific research resulting in scholarly publications](#). Legal teams use our document redaction capability to remove names, metadata, email addresses, and other sensitive information to produce Bates-stamped and spreadsheet-indexed PDF collections.

#Rstats backbone 2.0.0 can identify significant edges in bipartite projections like co-attendance, co-authorship, and co-sponsorship networks. Here's an example

Extracting the backbones of networks

```
install.packages("backbone")
library(backbone)
```


graph-tool

<https://graph-tool.skewed.de/>

graph-tool

Efficient network analysis

Download

Documentation

Mailing List

Git

Issues

What is graph-tool?

Graph-tool is an efficient [Python](#) module for manipulation and statistical analysis of [graphs](#) (a.k.a. [networks](#)). Contrary to most other Python modules with similar functionality, the core data structures and algorithms are implemented in [C++](#), making extensive use of [template metaprogramming](#), based heavily on the [Boost Graph Library](#). This confers it a level of [performance](#) that is comparable (both in memory usage and computation time) to that of a pure C/C++ library.

Download version 2.45

[Installation instructions](#) | [Changelog](#)

[Conda installation](#) (GNU/Linux | MacOS)

```
conda create --name gt -c conda-forge graph-tool
conda activate gt
```

►► It is *Fast!*

Despite its nice, soft outer appearance of a regular Python module, the core algorithms and data structures of graph-tool are written in C++, with performance in mind. Most of the time, you can expect the algorithms to run just as fast as if graph-tool were a pure C/C++ library. See a [performance comparison](#).

🧑‍🤝‍🧑 OpenMP Support

Many algorithms are implemented in parallel using [OpenMP](#), which provides excellent performance on multi-core architectures, without degrading it on single-core machines.

📖 Extensive Features

An extensive array of features is included, such as support for arbitrary vertex, edge or graph [properties](#), efficient "on the fly" [filtering](#) of vertices and edges, powerful graph I/O using the [GraphML](#), [GML](#) and [dot](#) file formats, graph [pickling](#), [graph statistics](#) (degree/property histogram, vertex correlations, average shortest distance, etc.), [centrality measures](#), standard [topological algorithms](#) (isomorphism, minimum spanning tree, connected components, dominator tree, [maximum flow](#), etc.), [generation of random graphs](#) with arbitrary degrees and correlations, [detection of modules and communities](#) via statistical inference, and much more.

👁 Powerful Visualization

Conveniently [draw](#) your graphs, using a variety of algorithms and output formats (including to the screen). Graph-tool has its own layout algorithms and versatile, interactive drawing routines based on [cairo](#) and [GTK+](#), but it can also work as a very comfortable interface to the excellent [graphviz](#) package.

📖 Fully Documented

Every single function in the module is documented in the docstrings and in the online [documentation](#), which is full of examples.

Network Tool (BETA)

[https://osome.iu.edu/tools/networks/?hashtag=metaverse&network type=rq&start date=2022-08-01&end date=2022-08-08](https://osome.iu.edu/tools/networks/?hashtag=metaverse&network%20type=rq&start%20date=2022-08-01&end%20date=2022-08-08)

Trends Tool (BETA)

https://osome.iu.edu/tools/trends/?hash_q=&text_q=safety%7Cmetaverse&start_date=2022-07-26&end_date=2022-08-08

Analyze the volume of tweets with a given hashtag, URL or keyword over a given period of time using the OSoMe decahose archive.

BotAmpALPHA

Compare likely bot activity in two sets of tweets

https://botometer.osome.iu.edu/botamp/?_gl=1%2avtzf1y%2a_ga%2aN Dg0NTAyMTk0LjE2NjI5NTAxNDU.%2a_ga_61CH0D2DQW%2aMTY2Mjk1MDE0NS4xLjAuMTY2Mjk1MDE0NS42MC4wLjA.

BotAmp^{ALPHA}

Compare likely bot activity in two sets of tweets

[What is BotAmp?](#) [How does BotAmp work?](#) [Why do I need to login?](#)

1. Search Twitter for tweets of interest with a query ⓘ

Query

Recent Popular Mixed ⓘ

2. Choose a baseline for comparison

Compare with your home timeline ⓘ

Compare with another query ⓘ

Check BotAmp!

Bot score distribution

Bot activity comparison

metaverse > **home timeline**

The likely bot activity of **metaverse** is significantly higher than that of your **home timeline** [show more](#)

AntConc

<https://www.laurenceanthony.net/software/antconc/>

The screenshot displays the AntConc software interface. The main window shows search results for the word "word". The interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, Settings, Help), a toolbar with various analysis options (KWIC, Plot, File, Cluster, N-Gram, Collocate, Word, Keyword), and a search panel on the left. The search panel shows the target corpus "AmE06_Learned" and the reference corpus "AmE06". The search results are displayed in a table with columns for File, Left Context, Hit, and Right Context. The search query is "word", and the results are sorted by frequency. The progress bar at the bottom indicates 100% completion, and the time taken for the KWIC display is 0.0043 ms.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
AmE06_J32.txt	ing word is a verb, but not when the -ing	word	is a noun or adjective. So the grammar of
AmE06_J47.txt	object, action or quality. Learning the category boundaries for each	word	is a specific "problem of induction." Children are placed
AmE06_J32.txt	a-hunting dog. The a- is possible when the -ing	word	is a verb, but not when the -ing word
AmE06_J34.txt	which coincides with word-initial position, and that the entire	word	is dominated by a single syllable. The gesture-calculations
AmE06_J59.txt	as Marjorie Perloff puts it, or perhaps that they put	word	and image in a mutually interpretive context, as the
AmE06_J59.txt	Stein's verbal portraits of these painters "attempt to fuse	word	and image," as Marjorie Perloff puts it, or perhaps
AmE06_J60.txt	an ancient purity and directness, a pre-Babelic unity of	word	and thing. In so doing, though, photography was just
AmE06_J47.txt	the word, or if the child understands and says the	word.	The second component is a list of 63 communicative, social,
AmE06_J47.txt	to indicate if they have heard their child say the	word.	The second major component utilizes an innovative sentence pair
AmE06_J47.txt	Consider what would appear to be the simplest condition of	word	learning. A fluent speaker of the language, such as
AmE06_J47.txt	MCDI and laboratory measures of comprehension, production, and	word	learning. The second is the Twins' Early Development Study (
AmE06_J47.txt	Each type of reference is a plausible use of the	word.	And even if we were correct in believing that "

graphlayouts

<https://github.com/schochastics/graphlayouts>

ggHoriPlot: build horizon plots in ggplot2

<https://rivasiker.github.io/ggHoriPlot/>

ggHoriPlot 1.0.0.9000

Get started

Reference

Articles ▾

Changelog

ggHoriPlot: build horizon plots in ggplot2

This package allows building horizon plots in ggplot2. You can learn more about the package in `vignette("ggHoriPlot")`.

Installation

You can install `ggHoriPlot` from CRAN via:

```
install.packages("ggHoriPlot")
```

You can also install the development version of the package from GitHub with the following command:

```
#install.packages("devtools")
devtools::install_github("rivasiker/ggHoriPlot")
```

Basic example

Load the libraries:

Simple repeat content along the human genome in 100 kb windows

NENO

NENO is a powerful note-taking app that helps you create your personal knowledge graph. With NENO, you retain full control over your data because you decide where it is stored: On your device, on a cloud storage of your choice, or even on a server under your control. <https://github.com/SebastianZimmer/neno>

The screenshot shows the NENO app interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with a profile icon, tabs for 'Jot Note', 'Read again', and 'Podcast on NENO', and statistics: 2.826 files, 3.472 links, and 10 tags (0.35%). Below the navigation bar is a search bar and a dropdown menu for 'Update date (descending)'. A list of notes is displayed on the left, with the 'Podcast on NENO' note selected and highlighted in blue. The right pane shows the detailed view of the 'Podcast on NENO' note, including a file named 'Podcast Episode 04.flac' (24.8 MIB) with a progress bar at 0:00 / 3:44. Below this, there's a section for 'Linked notes (3)' listing 'On the nature of information', 'Lovely Graph Algorithms', and 'Building a Second Brain'. At the bottom, there's an 'Add links' section.

PDFDataExtractor: A Tool for Reading Scientific Text and Interpreting Metadata from the Typeset Literature in the Portable Document Format

<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jcim.1c01198>

Top2Vec

<https://github.com/ddangelov/Top2Vec>

Top2Vec

Distributed Representations of Topics

Exploring UMAP parameters in visualizing single-cell spatially resolved transcriptomics data

<https://jef.works/blog/2022/01/19/exploring-umap-parameters/>

http://r-universe.dev/search/

Currently serving 11273 [packages](#), 21575 datasets, and 11059 [articles](#) by 5488 [maintainers](#) and 14113 contributors.

Not sure what to search for? Why not try: [maps](#), [bayesian](#), [ecology](#), [climate](#), [genome](#), [gam](#), [spatial](#), [database](#), [pdf](#), [shiny](#), [rstudio](#), [machine learning](#), [prediction](#), [birds](#), [fish](#), [sports](#), ... ([more popular topics](#))

Organizations

 yulab-smu					
 ropensci-review...					

Scientific Visualization: Python + Matplotlib

<https://github.com/rougier/scientific-visualization-book>

Web-GMap (arizona.edu)

GMap

```
graph {
  "0" [cluster="3", label="safety", pos="26.163,130.97"];
  "1" [cluster="3", label="accident", pos="270.82,243.14"];
  "2" [cluster="2", label="risk", pos="271.43,16.263"];
  "3" [cluster="2", label="hazard", pos="670.15,16.263"];
  "4" [cluster="2", label="injury", pos="415.11,16.263"];
  "5" [cluster="1", label="disaster", pos="513.44,131.26"];
  "0" -- "1";
  "1" -- "2";
  "0" -- "2";
  "3" -- "4";
  "5" -- "1";
  "5" -- "2";
}
```

...or try an example: [Sample](#), [Colors](#), [TradeLand](#), [MusicLand](#), [Recipes](#), [BookLand](#), [Universities](#)

Create Map

[Hide Advanced Options](#)

advanced options for map generation

Visualization Type:	GMap	Color Scheme:	blue to yellow
Layout Algorithm:	sfdp	Semantic Zoom:	<input type="radio"/>
Cluster Algorithm:	k-means	Spherical:	<input type="radio"/>
		Hyperbolic:	<input type="radio"/>

<https://circulum.io/twitter>

<https://github.com/koaning/bulk>

<https://prodi.gy/docs/text-classification#active-learning>

Bulk is a quick developer tool to apply some bulk labels. Given a prepared dataset with 2d embeddings it can generate an interface that allows you to quickly add some bulk, albeit less precise, annotations.

COVID19-Literature-Clustering

<https://github.com/MaksimEkin/COVID19-Literature-Clustering>

COVID19-Literature-Clustering

COVID-19 Literature Clustering

https://maksimekin.github.io/COVID19-Literature-Clustering/plots/t-sne_covid-19_interactive.html

https://maksimekin.github.io/COVID19-Literature-Clustering/maps/time_lapse.html

<https://www.kaggle.com/code/maksimeren/covid-19-literature-clustering>

<https://www.acemap.info/>

Make Academia Visible

Science bibliography

Search Papers

Science Hammer

<https://kg.hammerscholar.net/zh-hans/>

致力于计算机科学领域的科技文献数据挖掘
借助大数据和自然语言处理技术，从大规模科技文献中，提取结构化信息，构建学术知识图谱，为搜索、人机对话、推荐系统等提供基础支持。

数据规模

知识数量
21,192,755

实体种类
6

文献数量
5,397,648

关系种类
7

The screenshot displays the Science Hammer knowledge graph interface. On the left is a sidebar titled "实体目录" (Entity Directory) with a tree view of categories: Method, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Adversarial Learning, Multi-task Learning, Ensemble Methods, Discriminative Model, Generative Model, Representation Learning, Regression, Classification (highlighted), Graphical Models, and Clustering. The main area is titled "Classification" and shows a "科技知识图谱" (Technology Knowledge Graph) with a legend for relationship types: USED-FOR, FEATURE-OF, HYPONYM-OF, PART-OF, CONJUNCTION, COMPARE, and EVALUATE-FOR. The graph visualizes relationships between various classification tasks, such as "Image Classification" being a feature of "Image Classification System" and "Image Classification" being used for "Image-to-Image Translation".

https://github.com/axa-group/Parsr/blob/master/README_zh-cn.md

Parsr

Turn your documents into data!

build success

[Français](#) | [Portuguese](#) | [Spanish](#) | [中文](#)

- Parsr, is a minimal-footprint document (**image, pdf, docx, eml**) cleaning, parsing and extraction toolchain which generates readily available, organized and usable data in **JSON, Markdown (MD), CSV/Pandas DF** or **TXT** formats.

i2 Enterprise Insight Analysis

<https://i2group.com/>

The screenshot displays the IBM i2 Analyst's Notebook Premium software interface. The top menu bar includes File, Home, Arrange, Style, Analyse, Select, View, and Publish. The main workspace is divided into several panels:

- Map Panel:** Shows a map of the United States with several locations marked with red pins and labels: 4, Carfield Place; 4, Edward Avenue; 4, Howard's Lane; 4, Clarence Place; 4, Crooke Road; and 4, Stock Street.
- Network Graph Panel:** A large network graph visualization showing numerous nodes connected by lines, representing relationships between data points.
- Record Inspector Panel:** A window showing details for a selected record. The record is "4, Linstead Street Address". The properties section includes: Building Number (4), Street Name (Linstead Street), Town/City (Lovettsville), State (VA), and Geographic Location (Latitude: 39.2687, Longitude: 77.4396).
- Information Store Quick Search Panel:** A search results panel showing 5,089 records. The search criteria are "AC*" and "Exact match". The results list several records with details such as License Plate Number, Vehicle Type, Vehicle Make, and Vehicle Model.

The bottom status bar shows "Hidden Items: None Show All" and "Overview Pane Fit to Window Fit Selection to Window Actual Size Drag Chart".

Social Network Visualizer (SocNetV)

<https://socnetv.org/downloads>

IBM i2 Advanced Analytics and Intelligence

https://matplotlib.org/

Matplotlib: Visualization with Python

Matplotlib is a comprehensive library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations in Python. Matplotlib makes easy things easy and hard things possible.

- Create publication quality plots.
- Make interactive figures that can zoom, pan, update.
- Customize visual style and layout.
- Export to many file formats.
- Embed in JupyterLab and Graphical User Interfaces.
- Use a rich array of third-party packages built on Matplotlib.

Try Matplotlib (on Binder) →

`barbs(X, Y, U, V)`

Getting Started

Examples

Reference

Cheat Sheets

Documentation

Unstructured coordinates

Sometimes we collect data `z` at coordinates `(x, y)` and want to visualize as a contour. Instead of gridding the data and then using `contour`, we can use a triangulation algorithm and fill the triangles.

`tricontour(x, y, z)`

`tricontourf(x, y, z)`

`tripcolor(x, y, z)`

`triplot(x, y)`

Plotly Open Source Graphing Library for Python <https://plotly.com/python/>

plotly | Graphing Libraries

Search...

▼ Quick Reference

- Getting Started
- Is Plotly Free?
- Figure Reference
- API Reference
- Dash
- GitHub
- community.plotly.com

▼ Examples

- Fundamentals
- Basic Charts
- Statistical Charts
- Scientific Charts
- Financial Charts
- Maps
- AI and ML
- Visualizing Bioinformatics
- 3D Charts
- Subplots

Plotly Open Source Graphing Library for Python

Plotly's Python graphing library makes interactive, publication-quality graphs. Examples of how to make line plots, bar charts, error bars, box plots, histograms, heatmaps, subplots, multiple-axes, polar charts, and bubble charts. Plotly.py is [free and open source](#) and you can [view the source](#), [report issues](#) or [contribute on GitHub](#).

Deploy Python AI Dash apps on private Kubernetes clusters: [Pricing](#) | [Demo](#) | [Overview](#) | [AI App Services](#)

Fundamentals

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

[More AI and ML »](#)

ML Regression

kNN Classification

ROC and PR Curves

PCA Visualization

AI/ML Apps with Dash

Bioinformatics

[More Bioinformatics »](#)

Volcano Plot

Manhattan Plot

Clustergram

Alignment Chart

3D Charts

[More 3D Charts »](#)

3D Axes

3D Scatter Plots

3D Surface Plots

3D Subplots

3D Camera Controls

seaborn: statistical data visualization

<https://seaborn.pydata.org/>

seaborn: statistical data visualization

Seaborn is a Python data visualization library based on matplotlib. It provides a high-level interface for drawing attractive and informative statistical graphics.

For a brief introduction to the ideas behind the library, you can read the introductory notes or the paper. Visit the installation page to see how you can download the package and get started with it. You can browse the example gallery to see some of the things that you can do with seaborn, and then check out the tutorials or API reference to find out how.

To see the code or report a bug, please visit the GitHub repository. General support questions are most at home on stackoverflow, which has a dedicated channel for seaborn.

Contents

- Installing
- Gallery
- Tutorial
- API
- Releases
- Citing
- FAQ

Features

- **New** Objects: API | Tutorial
- Relational plots: API | Tutorial
- Distribution plots: API | Tutorial
- Categorical plots: API | Tutorial
- Regression plots: API | Tutorial
- Multi-plot grids: API | Tutorial
- Figure theming: API | Tutorial
- Color palettes: API | Tutorial

Example gallery

Apache ECharts

<https://echarts.apache.org/handbook/zh/get-started/>

折线图 line

基础折线图 Basic Line Chart

基础平滑折线图 Smoothed Line Chart

基础面积图 Basic area chart

折线图堆叠 Stacked Line Chart

堆叠面积图 Stacked Area Chart

渐变堆叠面积图 Gradient Stacked Area Chart

未来一周气温变化 Temperature Change in the Coming Week

折线图区域高亮 Area Pieces

数据过滤 Data Transform Filter

折线图的渐变 Line Gradient

一天用电量分布 Distribution of Electricity

大数据量面积图 Large scale area chart

Confidence Band

Rainfall vs Evaporation

Beijing AQI

Premonitions

Rainfall and Flow Relationship

Large Area Chart

Radial Polar Bar Label Position (middle)

极坐标柱状图标签 Radial Polar Bar Label Position

Tangential Polar Bar Label Position (middle)

极坐标柱状图标签 Tangential Polar Bar Label Position

世界人口总量 - 条形图 World Population

世界人口总量 World Population

阶梯瀑布图 (柱状图模拟) Waterfall Chart

堆叠条形图 Stacked Horizontal Bar

柱状图框选 Brush Select on Column Chart

多数值轴轴缩放 Mix Zoom On Value

多Y轴示例 Multiple Y Axes

柱状图动画延迟 Animation Delay

Neo4j

Neo4j Graph Database Books | Graph Machine Learning

可视化看中国

<http://vis.pku.edu.cn/vis4china/>

可视化看中国

赫赫中华，光被遐荒。越数千年，雄立东方。过去的几十年间，古老的中国在历经百年低谷之后在复兴中迸发出惊人的力量。中国社会在经济、科技、文化等方面发生了巨大的变化。回顾过去，“沧海桑田”，“翻天覆地”这样的文字已经不足以描述这一波澜壮阔而悠长的历史。幸运的是我们可以超越模糊的文字概念，借助可视化科技的力量，看到这片热土上已经或正在发生的奇迹。

2021年中国科学院、工程院新当选院士分布

工作单位所在地区

25 省级行政区

当选院士数量

149 人

芳翰流形 - 汜

《芳翰流形 - 流变》提供碑文整体赏析视觉表现和形状特征体的传承和变化。

注：数据来自中国科学院、工程院官网；高校附属医院合并统计；若同时列出2个单位，各单位各记0.5人；不含外籍院士。

工作单位所在地区 (共25个)

工作单位统计 (共117个)

2020年政府工作报告可视化

确保实现脱贫攻坚目标，促进农业丰收农民增收。

***** 说明 *****
1. 可视化展示可在词云和图表处进行交互
2. 鼠标悬停于动态词云展示报告相关内容
3. 鼠标点击动态词云可变更相关数据图表

CLIMATE TWEETOSCOPE

<http://tweetoscope.iscpif.fr/COP21/desktop.html?lang=EN>

CLIMATE TWEETOSCOPE
Science Twitter & Media

Le Tweetoscope Climatique
Everything You Always Wanted to Know About Climate Change

ISC-PIF/CNRS
David Chavaranas
Samuel Castillo
Mazyar Panahi

0:00 / 3:14

Research areas

- Biodiversité & extinctions
- Ressources en eau & irrigation
- Modèles climatiques
- Combustibles fossiles et émissions
- Photosynthèse & CO2 atmosphérique
- Matière organique & biomasse microbienne
- Société et politiques d'adaptation
- Agriculture et rendements
- Augmentation des températures
- Océan & Antarctique
- Surface des terres

from Jan 02 to Apr 23
47.206.086 tweets

Réfléchis @maxidabeny Dec 30, 2017
@FrancisLagneau_ @realDonaldTrump Non elle dit vrai mais la NASA n'a jamais dit que le réchauffement climatique é...
<https://t.co/WHrUzZzqLU>

Jean Paul Curtay @jeanpaulcurtay Feb 3, 2017
'Beyond the extreme': Scientists marvel at 'increasingly non-natural' Arctic warmth <https://t.co/9o90Wu4iE7> #CLIMAT

George Moore @erom51 Feb 16, 2017
Antarctica's Sea Ice Shrinks to New Record Low - GLOBAL WARMING? <https://t.co/AIX8lGpuC>

Craig @Craig_G432 Feb 2, 2018
@Russ01417768 @Alex_Mulcrow93 @piersmorgan <https://t.co/goh7JWwXok> That article is 2 years out of date

Evolution of total number of collected Tweets

Participate, explore and discover at climate.iscpif.fr

CLIMATE TWEETOSCOPE
Science Twitter & Media

Relative Attention

- Twitter
- Balanced
- Science

from Jan 02 to Apr 23
47.206.086 tweets

George Moore @erom51 Feb 16, 2017
Antarctica's Sea Ice Shrinks to New Record Low - GLOBAL WARMING? <https://t.co/AIX8lGpuC>

Stellane @Stellane Mar 23, 2017
Arctic sea ice shrinks to fourth lowest extent on record | Environment <https://t.co/loxFhmWzXy> #MerArctique

Brexshit & Trump #FBPE @BrexshitTrump Jan 31, 2018
Ice Caps at Record Low, Not High #Trump #UKIP #Brexhit #FactCheck <https://t.co/dmcMEF3Rya>

kc ashmore @kcashmore1 Feb 16, 2017
And further proof climate change is real Antarctica's Sea Ice Shrinks to New Record Low - National Geographic <https://t.co/OEwzHijCp>

Evolution of total number of collected Tweets

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GDELT GKG Network Visualization

[GDELT GKG Network Visualization \(gdeltproject.org\)](http://gdeltproject.org)

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References search for "safety science"

Substances | Reactions | Citing | Knowledge Graph | Save and Alert

Based on your query, we've returned the most relevant results. Would you like to load the entire result set?
[Learn about result relevance.](#)

[Load More Results](#)

222 Results

Sort: Relevance | View: Partial Abstract

1

The state of vaccine safety science: systematic reviews of the evidence.

By: Dudley, Matthew Z; Halsey, Neal A; Omer, Saad B; Orenstein, Walter A; O'Leary, Sean T; Limaye, Rupali J; Salmon, Daniel A
The Lancet. Infectious diseases (2020), 20(5), e80-e89 | Language: English, Database: MEDLINE

This Review updates the scientific evidence assessing possible causal associations of adverse events following immunisation (AEFI) compiled in the 2012 report from the Institute of Medicine and the 2014 report from the Agency for Healthcare Research and

Filter Behavior

Filter by

Document Type

- Journal (196)
- Review (59)
- Book (18)
- Commentary (2)

Filter Behavior

Filter by | Exclude

Document Type

- Journal (17)
- Review (9)
- Clinical Trial (1)
- Conference (1)
- Letter (2)
- Report (5)

Author

- Bussel, James B. (2)
- Cines, Douglas B. (2)
- George, James N (2)
- Gernsheimer, Terry (2)
- Godeau, Bertrand (2)

Citation Map for Immune thrombocytopenia associated with COVID-19 mRNA vaccine tozinameran - a clinical case and global pharmacovigilance data

Ratagay, Raphael; Istampoulouglou, Ioanna; Holbroa, Andreas; Buser, Andreas; Hirsiger, Julia R.; Eckstein, Jens; Berger, Christoph T.; Koehlin, Sarah; Leuppi-Taegtmeier, Michael
The Lancet. Infectious diseases (2021), 21(Dec.), w30084 | Language: English, Database: CPlus and MEDLINE

Full Text

Knowledge Graph from "safety science" References Search

Knowledge Graph Key

BETA

- References
- Authors
- Substances
- Concepts
- Organizations

Filter Behavior

Filter by | Exclude

Document Type

- Journal (126)
- Review (40)
- Book (18)
- Commentary (1)
- Conference (6)

[View All](#)

Language

- English (125)
- Japanese (13)
- Chinese (10)

中国科学院研究所学术画像

Academic Profile of CAS Institutes

CAS Institutions Profile(Statistical Report)
中国科学院研究所学术画像 (统计报告)

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CAS Science Structure Landscape
中国科学院研究所学术画像 (科学结构)

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科技文献数据预处理与统计分析系统(LDFAS)

科学结构图叠加分析系统(MSSS)

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科研机构计量评价分析系统(AIMES)

Home **Research Report** Academic Homepage Science Structure

Academic Profile of CAS Institutes 中国科学院研究所学术画像可视化系统 李杰 | Logout

Select Province

中国科学院物理研究所
Institute of Physics, CAS

研究领域: 凝聚态物理, 光学物理, 原子分子物理, 等离子体物理, 软物质物理, 凝聚态理论, 计算物理表面, 等离子体物理...
单位地址: 北京市海淀区中关村街道三环四环之间中关村南三街8号

进入机构画像 →

数据统计概览

Timespan	Documents	Sources
2006 : 2024	19754	1187
Documents Type	Authors	Institutions
15	20743	3393
Countries/Regions	Web of Science Categories	Research Areas
77	114	67
Author's Keywords	Keywords Plus	International Co-authorships
20166	15992	6916

Home Research Report **Academic Homepage** Science Structure

Academic Profile of CAS Institutes 中国科学院研究所学术画像可视化系统 李杰 | Logout

Map View Table View

Institutes list of Chinese Academy of Sciences

中国科学院化学研究所 Institute of Chemistry, CAS Documents:21960	
中国科学院大连化学物理研究所 Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics... Documents:19741	
中国科学院深圳先进技术研究院 Shenzhen Institute of Advanced Tec... Documents:15945	
中国科学院自动化研究所 Institute of Automation, CAS Documents:14654	
中国科学院地质与地球物理研究所 Institute of Geology & Geophysics, ... Documents:13610	
中国科学院福建物质结构研究所 (中国科... Fujian Institute of Research on the S... Documents:12299	
中国科学院上海有机化学研究所 Shanghai Institute of Organic Chem... Documents:11738	
中国科学院兰州化学物理研究所 Lanzhou Institute of Chemical Physi... Documents:10521	
中国科学院国家天文台 National Astronomical Observatory... Documents:10345	

国家战略科技力量科学结构可视化系统

Science Structure System of National Strategic S&T Forces

科研机构科学结构全景图
Science Structure of academic institutions

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中国科学院科学结构全景图
CAS Science Structure Landscape

Click here to access the system →

中国科学院文献情报中心2D展览全景图
Visual Dashboard (For 2D exhibition hall)

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Search Benchmarking Institutes

Switch layout Compare Analysis

Chinese Academy of Sciences

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)

University of London

CAS Benchmarking Institutes

Map of Science (6 Factors) Switch View

Switch layout Table View Insert Institution

Chinese Academy of Sciences

University of California System

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)

University of London

Harvard University

University of Texas System

Social Studies Biology & medical Environmental Sci & Tech Clinical Med Computer Sci & Eng Physical Sciences

学术画像在线展示系统

Online Gallery of Science Map

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Academic Profile of Outstanding Scientists

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重要学术机构学术画像
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Academic Profile of Leading Journals

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普赖斯获奖者画像
Price award winners Portrait

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引文索引数据采集系统(WDC)

科研机构计量评价分析系统(AIMES)

潘建伟院士

潘建伟，男，1970年3月生，浙江东阳人。1992年毕业于中国科学技术大学近代物理系，1995年获该校理论物理硕士学位，1999年获奥地利维也纳大学实验物理博士学位。中国科学院大学教授，中国科学院院士，发展中国家科学院院士，中科院量子信息与量子科技前沿卓越创新中心主任，教育部量子信息与量子科技前沿协同创新中心主任，中国科协副主席，中国青年科技工作者协会会长，全国青联副主席。潘建伟教授主要从事量子通信、量子计算和量子力学基础问题检验等方面的研究。作为国际上量子信息和量子通信实验研究领域的先驱和开拓者之一，他是该领域有重要国际影响力的科学家。利用量子光学手段，他在量子调控领域取得了一系列有重要意义的研究成果，尤其是他关于量子通信和多光子纠缠操纵的系统性创新工作使得量子信息实验研究成为近年来物理学发展最迅速的方向之一。

Items: 348 | Links: 6934 | Total link strength: 27516 | Clusters: 5

吴朝晖院士 (CN)

吴朝晖院士 (EN)

薛其坤院士 (EN)

李德仁院士 (EN)

郭华东院士 (CN)

胡海岩院士 (CN)

杨卫院士 (CN)

潘建伟院士 (EN)

Svante Pääbo (2022年获奖获得者) (EN)

Ronald Rousseau (PIF Scientist) (EN)

Guillermo Rein (PIF Scientist) (EN)

Ludo Waltman (EN)

Price award winners

Richard Klavans(USA)(1962)

Dick was inspired by Thomas Kuhn's insights into the structure of scientific revolutions and Henry Small's bibliometric approach to characterizing how research is structured and evolves. After completing his PhD in Economics at the University of Pennsylvania in 1989, he formed a company (SciTech Strategies) to make these insights useful to practitioners. In early years, the firm created large scale maps of research for practitioners in corporations (Abbott Labs, Astra Zeneca, Dupont, Glaxo, Kellogg, Kraft, Pfizer, SmithKline Beecham, and Unilever).

Overview Collaboration Network

Timespan

2001 : 2022

Documents

56

Sources

25

Documents Type

4

Authors

36

Institutions

36

Countries/Regions

11

Web of Science Categories

17

Research Areas

14

Author's Keywords

76

Keywords Plus

104

International Co-authorships

7

POS	获奖时间	获奖人	国籍	性别	出生年份	获奖年龄	文献数量	合作网络	控制
1	2023	Kevin Boyack	USA	男	1948	75	93	是	Update Data Analyze
2	2023	Richard Klavans	USA	男	1962	61	56	是	Update Data Analyze
3	2021	Ludo Waltman	The N...	男	1982	39	102	是	Update Data Analyze
4	2019	Lutz Bornmann	Germa...	男	1967	52	326	是	Update Data Analyze
5	2017	Judit Bar-Ilan	Israel	女	1958	59	122	是	Update Data Analyze
6	2015	Mike Thelwall	United...	男	1965	50	482	是	Update Data Analyze
7	2013	Blaise Cronin	USA	男	1949	64	104	是	Update Data Analyze
8	2011	Olle Persson	Sweden	男	1949	62	55	是	Update Data Analyze
9	2009	Michel Zitt	France	男	1947	62	41	是	Update Data Analyze
10	2009	Péter Vinkler	Hunga...	男	1941	68	77	是	Update Data Analyze
11	2007	Katherine W. ...	USA	女	1944	63	60	是	Update Data Analyze
12	2005	Howard D. Whi...	USA	男	1936	69	53	是	Update Data Analyze
13	2005	Peter Ingwersen	Denm...	男	1947	58	76	是	Update Data Analyze
14	2003	Loet Leydesdorff	The N...	男	1948	55	334	是	Update Data Analyze
15	2001	Leo Egghe	Belgium	男	1952	49	207	是	Update Data Analyze
16	2001	Ronald Rouse...	Belgium	男	1949	52	220	是	Update Data Analyze
17	1999	Henk F. Moed	The N...	男	1951	48	99	是	Update Data Analyze
18	1999	Wolfgang Glän...	Germa...	男	1955	44	214	是	Update Data Analyze
19	1997	Belver C. Griffith	USA	男	1931	66	17	是	Update Data Analyze
20	1997	Ben Martin	UK	男	1952	45	49	是	Update Data Analyze

BEIJING, CHINA MAINLAND

JIANGSU, CHINA MAINLAND

GUANGDONG, CHINA MAINLAND

NEW YORK, USA

BEIJING, CHINA MAINLAND

BEIJING, CHINA MAINLAND

JIANGSU, CHINA MAINLAND

GUANGDONG, CHINA MAINLAND

NEW YORK, USA

SHANGHAI, CHINA MAINLAND

MASSACHUSETTS, USA

ZHEJIANG, CHINA MAINLAND

TEXAS, USA

SHANDONG, CHINA MAINLAND

Social Studies Biology & medical Environmental Sci & Tech Clinical Med Computer Sci & Eng Physical Sciences

Map of Science (6 Factors)

BEIJING, CHINA MAINLAND

Social Studies Biology & medical Environmental Sci & Tech Clinical Med Computer Sci & Eng Physical Sciences

POS	机构名称	文章数量	数据状态
1	BEIJING, CHINA MAINLAND	178981	已上传
2	JIANGSU, CHINA MAINLAND	110395	已上传
3	GUANGDONG, CHINA MAINLAND	106480	已上传
4	NEW YORK, USA	96824	已上传
5	SHANGHAI, CHINA MAINLAND	89514	已上传
6	MASSACHUSETTS, USA	84682	已上传
7	ZHEJIANG, CHINA MAINLAND	75396	已上传
8	TEXAS, USA	71776	已上传
9	SHANDONG, CHINA MAINLAND	64579	已上传
10	HUBEI, CHINA MAINLAND	60368	已上传
11	SICHUAN, CHINA MAINLAND	55327	已上传
12	MARYLAND, USA	52415	已上传
13	ILLINOIS, USA	47330	已上传
14	FLORIDA, USA	45574	已上传
15	OHIO, USA	41300	已上传
16	NORTH CAROLINA, USA	40388	已上传
17	HUNAN, CHINA MAINLAND	38985	已上传
18	LIAONING, CHINA MAINLAND	37435	已上传
19	ANHUI, CHINA MAINLAND	35432	已上传
20	MICHIGAN, USA	35402	已上传

Home Map view Data view

Energy Storage Science Landscape (Batteries Part)
储能科学技术研究景观 (电池篇)

Basic Search [TAK-Topic Search] please input content Search Advanced Search

batchNo: 202405101415399021498

Refresh Export 2 WoS Export 2 CSV Export 2 Endnote Duplicates Deletion Top Cited Papers h-index Visualization Report Data Quality Delete

Setting Display Fields Filed Tags

POS	TI	SO	AU	DI	NR	PY	TC	NAU	NAUI	NAUC	CONTROL
1	software survey: vosviewe...	scientometrics	van eck, nj; waltm...	Full Text Link	37	2010	6387	2	4	1	Edit Delete
2	from louvain to leiden: g...	scientific reports	traag, va; waltman...	Full Text Link	25	2019	1151	3	2	1	Edit Delete
3	a unified approach to map...	journal of informetrics	waltman, i; van ec...	Full Text Link	37	2010	956	3	2	1	Edit Delete
4	the leiden manifesto for ...	nature	hicks, d; wouters, ...	Full Text Link	10	2015	814	5	8	3	Edit Delete
5	citation-based clustering...	scientometrics	van eck, nj; waltm...	Full Text Link	23	2017	781	2	2	1	Edit Delete
6	a review of the literatur...	journal of informetrics	waltman, i	Full Text Link	342	2016	624	1	2	1	Edit Delete
7	science of science...	science	fortunato, s; bergs...	Full Text Link	103	2018	551	14	22	5	Edit Delete
8	a smart local moving algo...	european physical journal b	waltman, i; van ec...	Full Text Link	31	2013	524	2	2	1	Edit Delete
9	bibliometric monitoring o...	scientometrics	nederhof, aj	Full Text Link	90	2006	524	1	2	1	Edit Delete
10	constructing bibliometric...	journal of informetrics	perianes-rodrigue...	Full Text Link	35	2016	512	3	3	2	Edit Delete
11	fatal attraction: concept...	scientometrics	van raan, afj	Full Text Link	28	2005	483	1	2	1	Edit Delete
12	how to normalize cooccurr...	journal of the american soci...	van eck, nj; waltm...	Full Text Link	90	2009	469	2	4	1	Edit Delete
13	comparison of the hirsch...	scientometrics	van raan, afj	Full Text Link	14	2006	426	1	2	1	Edit Delete
14	a comparison of two techn...	journal of the american soci...	van eck, nj; waltm...	Full Text Link	53	2010	413	4	5	1	Edit Delete
15	measuring contextual cita...	journal of informetrics	moed, hf	Full Text Link	28	2010	402	1	2	1	Edit Delete
16	journal impact measures i...	scientometrics	glanzel, w; moed, hf	Full Text Link	37	2002	397	2	3	3	Edit Delete
17	a new methodology for con...	journal of the american soci...	waltman, i; van ec...	Full Text Link	33	2012	385	2	2	1	Edit Delete
18	sleeping beauties in scie...	scientometrics	van raan, afj	Full Text Link	3	2004	383	1	2	1	Edit Delete

共 692 条 50条/页 < 1 2 3 4 5 6 ... 14 > 前往 1 页

Data Format: Web of Science Plain Text Project Title: Project Title Uploading Files Loading Data Open Projects Open CAS Profile

Process Report

Clear process report

Basic Search TAK-Topic Search please input content Search Advanced Search Current project : Safety Science 23

Parsing CR Export CR Current project : Ronald

Global Map of Science(Categories)

■ Social Studies ■ Biology & medical ■ Environmental Sci & Tech ■ Clinical Med ■ Computer Sci & Eng
■ Physical Sciences

[Open Categories Overlay →](#)

Global Map of Science(Journals)

■ Psychology, education, health ■ Mathematics, systems, mathematical ■ Medicine, medical, clinical
■ Molecular, biology, immunology ■ Physics, materials, chemistry ■ Biology, Chemical, Genetics
■ Neurology, sports, ophthalmology ■ Ecology, earth, marine ■ Economics, economic, political

[Open Journals Overlay \(Demo\) →](#)

Quick links

LMVP Home

CAS Portraits

Topics (电池)

Shared Project

Open Project

Global Map of Science(Categories)

■ Social Studies ■ Biology & medical ■ Environmental Sci & Tech ■ Clinical Med ■ Computer Sci & Eng
■ Physical Sciences

[Open Categories Overlay →](#)

Global Map of Science(Journals)

■ Psychology, education, health ■ Mathematics, systems, mathematical ■ Medicine, medical, clinical
■ Molecular, biology, immunology ■ Physics, materials, chemistry ■ Biology, Chemical, Genetics
■ Neurology, sports, ophthalmology ■ Ecology, earth, marine ■ Economics, economic, political

[Open Journals Overlay \(Demo\) →](#)

Quick links

LMVP Home

CAS Portraits

Topics (电池)

Shared Project

Open Project

Data Analysis

Selected WoS format

Frequency File

Upload WoS data

Loading data

Project lists

Large Language Modes

Benchmarking

Visualization report

Node Size

Slider control

Label Setting

Show label Hide label

Project Management

Open Projects

Remove Project

■ Psychology, education, health ■ Mathematics, systems, mathematical ■ Medicine, medical, clinical ■ Molecular, biology, immunology ■ Physics, materials, chemistry
■ Biology, Chemical, Genetics ■ Neurology, sports, ophthalmology ■ Ecology, earth, marine ■ Economics, economic, political

Cluster view Highlight view

POS	name	value
1	physical review d	79
2	annals of biomedical engineeri...	75
3	scientific reports	67
4	nature	63
5	journal of medical internet res...	59
6	journal of high energy physics	52
7	journal of the american medic...	49
8	urology	43
9	radiology	40
10	journal of vascular and interve...	40
11	international journal of surgery	39
12	plos one	35
13	american journal of bioethics	33
14	physics letters b	29
15	aesthetic surgery journal	27
16	aesthetic plastic surgery	27
17	computer	26
18	medical teacher	26
19	journal of chemical education	26
20	sensors	24
21	library journal	23
22	propellants explosives pyrotec...	23
23	journal of vascular surrerv	22

Process Report

Clear process report

Knowledge Matrix Analysis

Current matrix info: Collaboration-Regions 16*16

Matrix View Network Visualization Louvain Cluster **Chordal diagram** Circle Viz Tree map VOSviewer Online World Map

Type of Analysis

- Knowledge Evolution
- Collaboration**
- Co-Categories
- Co-Keywords
- References Co-Citation

Unit of analysis

- Authors
- Regions**
- Organizations

Threshold Setting

Number of items: 50

Data disambiguation

Edit items list

Matrix Generation

Matrix Construction

Matrix Visualization

Matrix 2 VOSviewer

Info

About KMV

No	Items	Freq
1	belgium	218
2	china, mainland	121
3	bangladesh	5
4	spain	5
5	uk	5
6	usa	5
7	hungary	4
8	netherlands	4
9	sweden	4
10	india	3
11	norway	3
12	cuba	2
13	france	2
14	germany	2
15	brazil	1
16	denmark	1

Knowledge Matrix Analysis

Current matrix info: Collaboration-Authors 50*50

Matrix View **Network Visualization** Louvain Cluster Chordal diagram Circle Viz Tree map VOSviewer Online

Type of Analysis

- Knowledge Evolution
- Collaboration**
- Co-Categories
- Co-Keywords
- References Co-Citation

Unit of analysis

- Authors**
- Regions
- Organizations

Threshold Setting

Number of items: 50

Data disambiguation

Edit items list

Matrix Generation

Matrix Construction

Matrix Visualization

Matrix 2 VOSviewer

Info

About KMV

Nodes setting

Nodes Types

Circles node Frames node

Node Size

Log node Original node

Node transparency

Node color Setting

More Colors...

Label setting

Label Setting

Show label Hide label

Label Size

Log label Original label

Label Color

More Colors...

Lines setting

Line Colors

More Colors...

Line Weights

Log line Original line

No	Items	Freq
1	rousseau, ronald	220
2	hu, xiaojun	30
3	egghe, leo	28
4	liu, yuxian	21
5	guns, raf	16
6	ye, fred y.	14
7	liang, liming	13
8	rousseau, sandra	11
9	zhang, lin	9
10	yang, liying	8
11	chen, jin	5
12	glanzel, wolfgang	5
13	mahbuba, dilruba	5
14	ahlgren, per	4
15	engels, tim c. e.	4
16	garcia-zorita, carlos	4
17	huang, shuiqing	4
18	rahman, a. i. m. jakaria	4
19	sanz-casado, elias	4
20	yan, sulan	4
21	zhong, zhen	4
22	ding, jielan	3

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How to Create an Overlay Map of Science Using the Web of Science

Ken Riopelle, Loet Leydesdorff, 李杰

电子邮件: lijie_jerry@126.com
科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerryueb>

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